

TEA

The
European Archaeologist

The newsletter of EAA members for EAA members
Issue 82 – Autumn 2024

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Cover

Beidha, Petra, Jordan. A Bedouin woman preparing bread in a *tabun* oven

Micaela Sinibaldi

University of Warsaw

Tabun ovens for the preparation of bread are part of a very long-standing culture in the Middle East. As part of a project aimed at reconstructing the history of Petra after the Byzantine period (which is traditionally but erroneously thought to be a substantial abandonment of the area) excavations by the *Islamic Baydha Project* at Beidha (Jordan) have investigated a village of the Middle Islamic period. Here, several domestic structures included *tabun* ovens that are identical to those still used today in the local environs. Current studies have shown that the material culture of Petra in the Islamic period is characterized by particularly intense longevity, including aspects of ceramic production technology, building techniques, and other elements of daily life.

The *Islamic Baydha Project* gives particular importance to the interaction and synergic effect of three major axes: archaeological research, archaeological training and community engagement. The project values a good understanding of recent and modern material culture from the local area. Such an understanding helps in the interpretation and understanding of archaeological remains when they were found, how those remains were used in life and the reasons behind the maintenance of long-lasting local traditions. For this reason, the team involves experienced individuals from the local community to create a better understanding of traditional building techniques and technological aspects. At the same time, this inclusive approach opens up the possibility for the local community to connect more closely with their own local cultural heritage and to the history of the community at the site.

This photo was taken during a visit of the team to a *tabun* in Beidha, to better understand and record the archaeological traces of a *tabun* found on the excavation. We learnt, also, that a local *tabun* lasts an average of 10-15 years.

As archaeologists, we often work within a living community who can provide us with information not only on the latest history of the site, but also on crucial aspects of the local material culture. Research-driven archaeology can be a powerful and fundamental part of the sustainable archaeology of the future, which must be relevant not only to archaeologists, but also to modern, local communities, and must, therefore, take us “out of the comfort zone” and put “fieldwork in perspective.”

The protection of the intangible cultural heritage of the Bedouins of Petra is also one of the current UNESCO projects in Jordan.

Letter from the Editors

The EAA is so much more than an Annual Meeting

Before we took up the editorship of *The European Archaeologist*, we regularly referred to the EAA's Annual Meeting as 'The EAA' as in "Are you going to this year's EAA (in wherever)"? After three years of sitting in on EAA Executive Board meetings and witnessing the incredible amount of work and dedication that EAA Officials, the Advisory Board, Secretariat and Members put into the Association every day, we are extremely confident in saying that, although the EAA Annual Meeting (or AM, as we now refer to it) *consistently* remains a professional highpoint of our calendar year, the EAA as European Association of Archaeologists is so very much more than its AM.

The Association is a democracy of like-minded individuals who are passionate about archaeology, cultural heritage, and the past in general. But it is also a community of academics, professionals and *ildsjæle* (to use a Danish term which literally means 'burning souls') who are concerned not only with the past but stridently with the present and future as well. With this in mind, we wish to address an important question: What does the EAA do outside of the AM? The answer—which is not always visible to many Members—is 'Very much, indeed!'

For example, the EAA has now just recently supported [the Benchmarks for Archaeology and Heritage protection](#) as a means of assessing different political parties' positions relative to archaeology and heritage, for the second time. The EAA is consulted by the Council of Europe in relation to archaeology, heritage management, and the historic landscape. This has been particularly important recently regarding on-going concerns surrounding the protection of the environment as a human right ([Hüglin 2024, TEA 80](#)).

The Association promotes European archaeology and European archaeologists on the EU level, e.g. through support of the European Archaeology days (for more information, see [Ratier 2022, TEA 74](#); [Reiter 2023, TEA 76](#) and [Khomenko 2023, TEA 76](#)) and it represents the same on an international level (e.g. at the SAA conferences in the US and by the recent rapprochement with UK-based CifA, which you can read more about in [this issue](#)).

The EAA is also vested in the interests of archaeologists themselves. This is exemplified through the [Oscar Montelius Foundation](#)'s continual furnishing of grants and bursaries for the attendance of the AM and the recent promotion of the [Karen E. Waugh Foundation](#) and their support of archaeological initiatives involved with the North Sea region. The EAA has also recently established an Anti-Harassment Board/Committee dedicated to the protection of Members, and the *European Journal of Archaeology* promotes research and young researchers through its yearly [Student Award](#). For more senior Members, it also hosts [job announcements](#) that aid many Members to advance their careers.

In addition to all of this, the EAA also provides dissemination of archaeological research, activities, and dialogues through its publications: the *European Journal of Archaeology* ([EJA](#)), the monograph series 'Themes in Contemporary Archaeology' ([THEMES](#)), and of course this very newsletter ([TEA](#)). Of exciting note in these regards, as of 16 October of this year, the *EJA* will transition to an open access format in a significant move to encourage academic parity and to increase the visibility and scope of

dissemination of archaeological work (see [Announcements](#)). Further, the EAA provides a number of other [prizes and awards](#) that celebrate excellence in scholarship and encourage and support early career researchers; not least of these are the [Book Prize](#) and the [Heritage Prize](#), both of which are prestigious recognition of scholarly achievements in our field.

What first really brought home the idea of what it meant to be a member of the EAA community (and here we mention not topic-specific Communities, but rather the network of Members) was following the first few days of the invasion of Ukraine. To us, it seemed that the EAA Secretariat was acting not unlike the archaeological equivalent of NASA headquarters in Huston, TX (USA), fielding calls and emails from archaeologists around the world as members offered guest rooms for displaced colleagues and temporary storage space for fragile objects fleeing the conflict, among many other offers of aid and outreach. It was but one shining instance of just how much of a community the Association is. For example, there were regular updates on EAA social media about which passes were open, so that colleagues were informed in real time about how and where they could get out of the country safely. It bears re-emphasizing here that this was all also *within the archaeological community of the EAA*. For those colleagues who did choose to stay in Ukraine, the EAA supported and facilitates a not-so-secret underground literature exchange, allowing colleagues in Ukraine to gain access to the literature they need to continue to conduct research and protect cultural heritage, sometimes at the very front lines of the on-going conflict ([TEA 74](#)).

It should also be mentioned that the EAA is a non-profit organization. Its officers and editorial teams are not paid; their hard work is voluntary. Speaking of volunteers, the student volunteers that work so diligently at every AM are an outstanding example of the dedication and hard work for which we and our growing membership should be extremely grateful. (Thank you volunteers!!!) It is our opinion that the strength of the EAA community on the global scale is reflected in its growing numbers; at latest count these now include 5,774 archaeologists and heritage professionals around the world.

As such, the EAA possesses a potentially tremendous amount of people power. As we move forward as a community of *ildsjæle*, we can expect to make adjustments and strategies that will allow us to accommodate the Association's growth and scope. Things will change—as students of the past, we of course know this to be true. However, as far as we are concerned, we are proud to say that we are Members of the EAA. We appreciate the many things that our organization does both 'on stage' as well as behind-the-scenes.

Of course, the AM is a part of all of this. We believe that the AM is the point that kicks off many of the partnerships, project ideas, article recruitments, papers and research of the subsequent 12 months. However, what we love best about the EAA is not the end of August/start September AM in and of itself (though the impetus it gives the initiatives, collaborations, and working groups to come in the following year is a huge bonus), but rather what it does and continues to do to build community, protect heritage and advocate for colleagues the whole year long.

We were delighted to see so many of you at the AM, and wish you all many successful initiatives and collaborations until we meet again in Belgrade. In the meantime, we hope that this issue may whet your appetite and tide you over until 2025. We include the usual *TEA* fare: our [cover](#) (which represents the final winner from the 2023 photojournalism competition), the [EAA Member Calendar](#), the ever popular [In Case You Missed it](#) and chats with EAA Official [Elin Dalen](#) of the OMF and Member [Javier Mejuto](#).

We include overviews of a recent [Bronze Age boat building project](#) in the UK and the [EAMENA Project's amazing results](#) on heritage monitoring via Machine Learning. Additionally, there is a thought-provoking article on using [generative AI for sharpening research questions](#) and a wonderful discussion on recent work studying the [mobility and integration of the formerly enslaved](#) in the ancient Greek world and a sneak peek into a key [recent discovery of a Vučedol clay wheel](#) from Transdanubia.

This issue is also focused on discussions of the discipline, professionalism and the EAA itself. These include [a debate on the future for European professional institutions for archaeology](#), a [review of the EAA AM](#), a [debate on where the EAA should go next](#) as well as a [reply to the latter by EAA President Eszter Bánffy](#). There is a notice on [recommendations for the teaching of history and other news from CINGO](#) as well as an insight piece on [the ICOMOS International Charter for Cultural Heritage Tourism](#) and Community News about a [recent visit by the Community on Archaeology and Tourism's recent visit to Ostia antica](#).

We also wanted to express our thanks to [Theresa Airey](#), [Charles W. Bowers](#) and [Sandy LeBrun-Evans](#) who once again acted as members of the *TEA* photojournalism competition jury to select the five entries that moved on to the competition semi-final. EAA Members made the final decision, voting for the three winning entries by means of the EAA Annual Survey. *TEA* congratulates members Heide Wrobel Nørgaard, Nicolas Vanderesse and João Vinícius Chiesa Back on being the winners of 2025's Photojournalism Competition 'Archaeology: Art or Science'. In addition to being *TEA*'s 'Photojournalists of the Year', the aforementioned winners will have their work featured on the 2025 covers of *TEA*, and each will receive one year's gratis membership to the EAA.

Thank you to all of those you participated, and all of those who voted! You and your continued dedication and passion for archaeology and heritage make *TEA* what it is, certainly, but also make the EAA an Association of which we are proud to be members.

Before closing this issue with some important [Announcements](#), we include a [remembrance of Prof. Timothy Darvill](#), who was not only a respected professional but also a dear friend to many and who will be sorely missed.

Best regards,

Samantha S. Reiter & Matthew J. Walsh

Editors

Calendar for EAA Members

October 2024 – February 2025

mid Oct / early Nov	Registration for the 31st EAA Annual Meeting in Belgrade opens
October / November	Call for EAA Book Prize nominations opens
31 October	Deadline for session proposals for the 31st EAA Annual Meeting in Belgrade, Serbia
13 December	Announcement of session acceptance / rejection to session organisers
18 December	Deadline for registration and membership payment for session organisers
20 December	Call for papers for the 31st EAA Annual Meeting in Belgrade, Serbia, opens
23 December – 6 January	EAA Secretariat closed
31 December	End of the 2024 EAA membership
1 January	Beginning of the 2025 EAA membership
January	Call for nominations to the EAA election circulated to Members
January	Call for nominations to the European Heritage Prize circulated to Members
January	Call for nominations to the Oscar Montelius Foundation (OMF) Early Career Achievement Prize (ECAP) circulated to Members
1 January	Deadline for submissions to TEA winter issue
29 January	Final payment deadline (registration and membership fee) for all session organisers
30 January	Final list of sessions and session organisers for the 31st EAA Annual Meeting in Belgrade, Serbia, available
3 February	Call for volunteers opens
6 February	Deadline for paper submissions
28 February	Call for volunteers closes
28 February	Deadline for EAA Book Prize nominations

In Case You Missed It...

Joana Valdez-Tullett

EAA Social Media Editor

[French dig team finds 200-year old note from archaeologist](#)

[Bones reveal first evidence of Down Syndrome in Neanderthals](#)

[Ancient family burials tell the story of migration that reshaped Europe](#)

[Infant burials found under prehistoric “dragon stone”](#)

[Should the Stone Age be called the Wood Age?](#)

[Neolithic site in Orkney reburied after 20 years of excavation](#)

[Meet the Stone Age Trøndelag](#)

[UGR researchers exhume bodies of 10 victims from a mass grave in Granada](#)

All images from flaticon.com

Notice

Recommendation on History Teaching in Europe and other news from the Conference of International NGOs Autumn Session in Strasbourg

Sophie Hüglin

EAA Commissioner to the Conference of INGOs to the Council of Europe

From 14-16 October 2024, the Conference of INGOs (CINGO) held its hybrid [Autumn Session](#) in Strasbourg. See Figure 1. Of special relevance to archaeologists and heritage practitioners is the Council of Europe's (CoE) current focus on [History Education](#) as it is – also in archaeology – a current trend to support nationalistic and revisionist views of the past. To this the CINGO is contributing its [Recommendation on History Teaching in Europe](#) that has been drafted by the Federation for European Education (FEDE) and then revised and voted on in the plenary carefully avoiding a possible conflict with teachers academic freedom. This document will contribute to the Annual Meeting of the [Observatory on History Teaching in Europe](#) (OHTe) which will take place in Strasbourg and online 5-6 December 2024. As preparation it will be worthwhile to consult with OHTe's [General Report on the State of History Teaching in Europe](#).

Figure 1. Gerhard Ermischer, the President of the Conference of INGOs at the Council of Europe. Moderating the hybrid Autumn Session in Strasbourg (screenshot SH).

Engaging with the topics that are currently discussed within the CoE, that is what all three guest speakers – [Gianluca Esposito](#), Director General of Human Rights and Rule of Law, [Aoife Nolan](#), Chairperson of the European Committee of Social Rights and Urska Umek, Head of Democratic Institutions and Civil Society – recommended to the INGOs assembled in the Conference. This of course is not easy with the new internal structures that are just taking up their work and with with CoE's new Secretary General [Alain Berset](#) who has been elected in September 2024 by the Parliamentary Assembly (PACE) for a term of five years. Therefore a publication has come out to give orientation on the [CoEs Intergovernmental Committees and their Roles and Responsibilities](#). Of special interest for archaeologists here are: the [Ad hoc Multidisciplinary Group on the Environment](#) (GME) that is to develop a comprehensive strategy on the environment and a related action plan, with a view to adoption at the Ministerial session in May 2025. This is the Intergovernmental Steering Committee that is to implement the [2023 Reykjavik Declaration](#). Its main goal is addressing the [Triple Planetary Crisis](#) as defined by United Nations from a human rights perspective.

Another Intergovernmental Committee is the [Steering Committee for Culture, Heritage and Landscape](#) (CDCPP) which is even closer linked to the CoE Conventions relevant for archaeologists. Already in 2021, for the 30th anniversary of the Valetta Convention the CDCPP held a thematic session on [Archaeology and digital technologies](#) which also analysed the Convention's successes, but also the obstacles and challenges as well as the future prospects and opportunities.

Civil Society organisations – as some prefer to call NGOs – and especially the ones active internationally are important to the CoE because they can provide independent data on their sector documenting positive or negative developments. See Figure 2. Such data and reports can be used in periodic examinations and country reports by the respective CoE entities to remind member states of the CoE conventions they signed. This has two phases: firstly, the need to implement them in the national legislation and secondly to enforce them on a daily basis. For European archaeology and heritage management such data and independent reports are still the exception. Currently, the [Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe](#) (DISCO) project that examined the archaeological labour market in this respect was the first and the last on a European scale.

Reelected [CINGO President Gerhard Ermischer](#) and his Standing Committee presented the CINGOs revised [Three-Year Strategy \(2024-2027\)](#). A prior survey among the CINGO members had given them the opportunity to state their key priorities and so influence the strategies wording. Very high up in these priorities are promoting “democracy by civil society participation”, the [Human Rights convention](#) and the [European Social Charter](#). ON the other hand, “heritage, culture and landscape” or “LGBTQ-rights” were ranking at the lower end. Specific strategies had been developed on [gender equality](#) – presented by [Anita Schetzer-Spranger](#) from ZONTA International – and [youth](#) – presented by [Ece Ciftci](#) from SosyalBen.

Figure 2. Representatives of International NGOs attending the CINGO Autumn Session in Strasbourg (screenshot SH).

In the CINGO there are currently eight thematic [Committees](#). For EAA it would be sensible to join “[Inclusive territories, environment and health](#)”. That would mean to dedicate more time and effort than one EAA Commissioner usually can offer. This is the moment to thank my Jesper de Raad for serving as EAA Co-Commissioner and as youth delegate to the CINGO for the last four years. It is up to the EAA Executive Board now to find a suitable way in how to strengthen EAAs delegation at the CINGO to make full use of its participatory status.

Chat with EAA Official over TEA

Elin Dalen

Institution: Retired. I worked for the Directorate of Cultural Heritage in Norway for 37 years and retired in 2023.

Position in the EAA: Oscar Montelius Foundation Trustee (chair)

EAA Member since: 1993

At left: June, 2024 UNESCO world heritage site of Trogir, Croatia. The last few years at the Directorate for Cultural Heritage in Norway, Dalen worked with world heritage both on a national and international level. Photo courtesy of E. Dalen.

TEA: Why do you do archaeology/How did you decide to do it?

Dalen: The summer when I was ten years old, a childhood friend borrowed a book from the library about Tutankhamon which we read together. I didn't understand much, but a flame was lit. Later, as a student and in my work life I began to realize the importance that archaeology has to social development and as a part of people's lives – an importance that is often underestimated. One cannot have a life or a society without anchoring it in the past. I have always been curious about how people lived their lives in earlier times. For instance, how was it to give birth and raise children during the Stone Age, or to travel over long distances in Roman times?

TEA: What is the most important and relevant part of your work?

Dalen: Through the years I have had many different positions in the EAA. Since 2019, I have been a Trustee of the Oscar Montelius Foundation (OMF). I find the work for the Foundation very important, as OMF disposes and distributes some money which is used to the benefit of EAA Members. OMF supports Members to go to conferences to present their work and take part in Communities, helping members share knowledge and to network.

This year OMF has established a Strategic Plan for the period 2025-2028, published at <https://www.e-a-a.org/OMF>. I also believe that the OMF Early Career Achievement Prize plays an important role for young archaeologists as their work is acknowledged. We (the

Trustees) are very impressed by what young archaeologists achieve and contribute, both to archaeology as such, and to society.

Above: EAA AM's Opening Ceremony with prize winner, Louise de Mello and the three OMF Trustees. Alongside Dalen (front left) are Margaret Gowen and Arek Marciniak. Photo courtesy of E. Dalen.

TEA: What is the biggest issue facing archaeology today?

Dalen: I fear the growth of separatism and nationalism that is often combined with the misuse of scientific knowledge for political purposes and the widespread deployment of misinformation. I think it is important that archaeologists use their voice to protect democratic values and preserve cultural heritage.

TEA: What archaeology literature are you reading right now?

Dalen: As I'm part of a project about ship burials dating to the Viking Age, I'm reading articles and books about the Viking Age. I have just finished Cat Jarman's book *The Bone Chest, Unlocking the Secrets of the Anglo-Saxons*. The next book I plan to read is written by Synnøve Vinsrygg and is about a powerful sorceress and her ancestors living in the north of Norway between 550-750.

TEA: If you could go back in time, would you go? If so, where and when?

Dalen: I have always been fascinated by the Bronze Age, particularly the big changes occurring during the period and how those changes influenced contemporary societies and people's

lives. Taking a glance into daily life, processions, the use of new materials, trade and travel would be fascinating and intriguing to my mind.

TEA: Any advice to new archaeologists just starting out?

Dalen: Follow your heart. Then you become good at what you are doing. Take chances and move around, whether it is in your own country or abroad. I think it is important to ask what I can do for archaeology and society and not only what others can do for me.

TEA: Does archaeology have relevance to current events? If yes, how?

Dalen: One of our time's biggest challenges is climate change. One way of handling climate change is to use traditional knowledge. Archaeologists know how equivalent challenges have been solved in earlier times. For instance, in response to climate change, we may suggest how to change from today's crops to more drought-tolerant crops and practice more sustainable agriculture and/or how to re-use old—and often forgotten—irrigation systems.

TEA: Some people say that culture (broadly speaking) is a luxury. Do you agree or disagree? Why do you think that is?

Dalen: In my view, culture is crucial for any society. What would a society be without culture to bind people together? Culture and cultural heritage are essential to societies and communities. Cultural heritage shapes identity and is the glue between people and societies.

Above: Photo taken as part of an excavation project on Mørstadstølen ved Vinstervann, Innlandet County, Norway. Photo by Kristine Johansen, Directorate of Cultural Heritage, Norway.

Meet a Member over TEA

Javier Mejuto

Institution: Space Sciences Faculty, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de Honduras

Position: Dean

EAA Member since: 2018

Image at left courtesy of J. Mejuto.

TEA: Why do you do archaeology/How did you decide to do it?

Mejuto: To be honest, it has been quite a journey. I have always had a great interest in various fields of knowledge, in particular astronomy and the study of the past. I never thought of being able to combine those two areas of knowledge until I met my future supervisors for my doctoral thesis: Maria de Gracia Rodríguez-Caderot and Maria Luisa Cerdeño. Both of these researchers worked in an incipient field in Spain: archaeoastronomy (within cultural astronomy) in the Celtiberian cultural sphere. I quickly understood that this was the field for which I was looking. Within two weeks, I was involved in my postgraduate studies in archaeology and prehistory at the Complutense University of Madrid.

TEA: What is the most important and relevant part of your work?

Mejuto: In my opinion, cultural astronomers have changed the view we have of people in the past in several respects, both within and outside the professional field of archaeology. The very idea that human groups dedicated their time to the methodical observation of the sky and that the resulting knowledge was culturally applied to aid in their survival and adaptation within their geographical space still moves some preconceived ideas within archaeology today. Even more so if, as we know, this is applicable in any cultural region and in any temporal record.

I could tell many anecdotes from my fieldwork in archaeological projects that illustrate the different paths that archaeoastronomy has taken across Europe and the Americas. As a discipline, its history has been more complicated in Europe from its first steps. However, more and more researchers are approaching cultural astronomers in order to better understand how some ideas, worldviews and other aspects of culture that do not preserve in the material record can be revealed through cultural studies of celestial space.

Image above shows Mejuto and colleague working at Ayasta rock art shelter petroglyphs and astromorphs, Honduras. The settlement associated with the shelter is known, but the ethnic affiliation of the inhabitants is unknown. An approximate date of 1000 BCE is considered. The site includes geometric elements, on which the first rays of the Sun fall at sunrise in the winter solstice. Likewise, there are cavities on the wall resembling beads of time periods. There are also possible representations of astronomical events such as a solar eclipse and solar rituals, in both cases humans appear associated with these rock art stations. Image courtesy of J. Mejuto.

TEA: How do you see archaeology changing in the future?

Mejuto: Archaeology is changing before our very eyes. Perhaps the best example is the emergence of space archaeology. I highly recommend taking a look at the archaeological project that has been led by Dr. Justin St. P. Walsh and Dr. Alice Gorman carried out on the International Space Station since 2015 (<https://issarchaeology.org>). Related to cultural heritage, the ICOMOS initiative for Aerospace Heritage (<https://iscah.icomos.org>) is also very interesting and I have been strongly involved in that initiative since its creation.

I believe that this is the future that we will see in archaeology: principally studies that break the classic limits of archaeology and expand its validity as a field of study.

TEA: What archaeology literature are you reading right now?

Mejuto: I am currently reading several volumes of Springer's Historical & Cultural Astronomy series, in particular *Archaeoastronomy in the Roman World* and *Astronomy in the Ancient World: Early and Modern Views on Celestial Events*.

I am also re-reading Dr. Alice Gorman's book, *Dr Space Junk vs The Universe: Archaeology and the Future*. If you have not seen it, go and get it, because it will undoubtedly expand your conceptions of what archaeology is and can be!

TEA: Describe your workspace in five words or less.

Mejuto: Neat, but full.

TEA: What is the one piece of gear that you cannot live without in the field?

Mejuto: In addition to the classic ones that we all use, due to my specialty I use some less conventional pieces of gear. Perhaps the most useful for quick horizon analysis is the clinometer, along with a compass and GPS. These tools help me to rule out in many cases possible astronomical orientations of archaeological structures compared to others that I later analyze in specialized software.

Image above shows Mejuto visually analyzing the horizon profile from the archaeological site of Cubillejo de la Sierra, Guadalajara, Spain. The Visigoth necropolis of Cubillejo de la Sierra (Guadalajara, Spain) was initially excavated in the 2006-2007 campaign (when the photo was taken) as part of the investigation of the oppidum of Los Rodiles related to early Celtiberian pottery from a previous excavation in the vicinity of the hermitage of the Virgen de la Vega. Remains of Roman settlements and rock art also appear in the same area. Photo by Marta Chordá.

TEA: What is moment in archaeology has marked you most?

Mejuto: I will comment on one of the anecdotes that I referred to earlier. I was quite a bit younger at the time and during my first year of work the director of the excavation approached me to ask me if it was true that I studied astronomical knowledge in the past. I told him that it was true and when I began to explain in more detail what it consisted of, he angrily left, waving his arms in the air and shouting that it was nonsense because people in the past were too busy to look at the stars! I always remember that anecdote and how diagnostic it really is of some schools of thought. Far from offending me, that reaction (along with many others), helped me over time to understand archaeology in a better light and the role of cultural astronomy in understanding cultures in the past.

TEA: Any advice to new archaeologists just starting out?

Mejuto: The best advice I can give to young people entering this exciting field is not to stay in archaeology alone. Read and pursue everything you can outside the field. When I started, Geographic Information Systems, LIDAR, drones, and anything that smelled of technology was considered to be something for other professionals and in the best of scenarios archaeologists were only interested in the final data that these technologies could generate for their research. As my training is different from the standard, I always ran away from those ideas and tried to smooth the transition to new technologies for my fellow archaeologists.

Archaeology has changed a lot in the last decades and continues to change. There are more and more specialties in archaeology that are improving archaeological research by incorporating new sources of information into the study of human cultures and their pasts. So young people, do not be complacent with the current visions of archaeology; look for ways that you can improve them!

Project Overview

The Big Bronze Age Boat Build: Bronze Age crafting on the waterways of the Nene Valley, UK

Nadia Norman

Stanwick Lakes Nature Reserve, Rockingham Forest Trust, Northamptonshire, UK

Nestled in the heart of the Nene Valley in Northamptonshire, UK is Stanwick Lakes, a 750-acre nature reserve boasting a SSSI status (Site of Special Scientific Interest) for the conservation of birds and wildlife. See Figure 3. The site is managed by Rockingham Forest Trust, an environmental charity with a mission to create and conserve special green spaces and explore local heritage in ways which educate, involve and inspire.

Figure 3. Stanwick Lakes Nature Reserve – photo credit Emma Jones / Ancient Craft.

As with many river valleys throughout the UK, the Nene Valley – which runs from Peterborough down to Northampton – was formed tens of thousands of years ago as a glacial valley. The river basins that were formed were fertile and sheltered, making them perfect locations for hunting, settlement and eventually farming by the early inhabitants. In the 1980s, archaeological excavations conducted prior to gravel quarrying uncovered evidence of over 10,000 years of human occupation. From prehistoric barrows to Roman villas and Medieval villages, the Stanwick Lakes area was declared one of the most extensive and nationally significant archaeological sites of its time in Britain.

The excavations also unearthed over 20 Neolithic and Bronze Age monuments dating from 5000 – 1000 BC, including mounds, enclosures and barrows, all constructed along the river valley. With the addition of timber platforms, riverside structures and several rich inhumation and cremation burials, the site was described as having a clear and significant ritual purpose during these periods and would have made for an impressive prehistoric landscape (Harding & Healy 2013).

The geographical proximity to other well-known prehistoric sites increases the significance of this prehistoric landscape. Sites such as the Flag Fen Basin and Must Farm at Peterborough are wetland sites reminiscent of Stanwick Lakes and sit only 23 miles away as the crow flies. During the early Bronze Age, the River Nene flowed along the southern edge of the Flag Fen Basin – the same river that flows through the Nene Valley and Stanwick Lakes.

It is this continual use of the river valley for over 5000 years that has encouraged Stanwick Lakes to explore and tell the story of the heritage of the site and the wider area through engaging volunteer-led projects supported by The National Lottery Heritage Fund. Past projects have encouraged visitors to learn about historical eras through traditional crafting, educational programs and experiential historical builds. With the river being a key aspect of the landscape for trade, food and travel, it was imperative to encompass this into the current heritage project too.

In 2022, our latest three-year heritage project began with the aim of exploring the Bronze Age and Iron Age areas of the site (2,500 BC – 43 AD).

The project focussed on four main areas:

- Construction of a replica Iron Age settlement,
- Conservation of the remaining Bronze Age round barrow (a scheduled monument),
- Recreating Iron Age textiles with the Northants Guild of Spinners, Weavers and Dyers,
- Constructing a replica Bronze Age boat - what was to become the Big Bronze Age Boat Build

In 2023, a group of volunteers came together at Stanwick Lakes with Dr James Dilley of Ancient Craft, prehistoric specialist and experimental archaeologist. The volunteers were a diverse mix of woodworkers and enthusiasts with varying backgrounds including teaching, the fire service, and even archaeologists.

This 'Discovery Day' was an opportunity for the group to meet, share their own knowledge, to learn about Bronze Age log boat discoveries from across Europe and to explore the materials and techniques used that might influence the Big Bronze Age Boat Build project. One obvious choice for discussion and research were the log boat discoveries from Must Farm, Peterborough – one of the best-preserved Bronze Age settlements in the UK (Robinson, et al. 2014). The findings from Must Farm and other research from across Europe were used to give the build team a basic understanding relating to the various crafting techniques used to construct the log boats (Johnstone, et al. 2013).

An essential aspect of the project was that the build would utilise traditional and archaeologically-accurate replicas of bronze tools in order to keep the experience of crafting the vessels as authentic as possible. The team created their tools in bronze casting sessions with Dr James Dilley, learning how to make the bronze axe and adze heads using sand moulds. See Figure 4. Timber for hafting the tools

was sourced from the woodlands on site. Participants experimented with different binding materials based on archaeological finds. This experiential and experimental approach would become one of the true passions of the volunteer team and come to underpin the entire project.

Figure 4. Bronze axe and adze heads made by volunteers. photo credit Emma Jones / Ancient Craft.

The desire to find a sustainable source of wood for the log boats led to a partnership with the park team at Boughton House Estate, a stately home near Kettering, Northamptonshire. The Boughton House Estate park team had several lime trees that had fallen during a storm. The fallen lime branch was split into three sections, with the longest of the three measuring 4.5m long (14.7ft). The timbers were delivered to Stanwick Lakes by the 118 Close Support Group REME, Northampton on the back of their Army Reserve vehicles, thanks to a fantastic volunteer link with the regiment. See Figure 5. Thus, with the tools made and the logs delivered, the Big Bronze Age Boat Build began! Every aspect of the build took place in the outdoor crafting area at Stanwick Lakes, with visitors encouraged to observe and ask questions as the project progressed.

Figure 5. Members of 118 Close Support REME after delivering the lime logs. photo credit Emma Jones / Ancient Craft.

In June 2023, the team and Dr James Dillely started by stripping the bark. The bark strips thereby produced were soaked in the lake behind the boat yard and later harvested for lime bast to make cordage. The next stage was to look at the natural shape of each log section to work out where the logs would need to be split. Using the bronze tools, wooden wedges and mallets manufactured by the team, crafters worked at splitting and removing sections of each log to get as close to the log boat shape as possible. See Figure 6.

Figure 6. The team split the first log photo credit Emma Jones / Ancient Craft.

One of the logs had been earmarked for experimentation via an alternative technique (burning), which had been noted as a possible crafting method from the Must Farm log boats. A fire was set within a small area directly on the log and monitored as a controlled burn to approximately 2 cm before the burned material was scraped away and the burn was allowed to continue. It was a careful, gradual process, which provided interesting results. See Figure 7. The most time-consuming part of the burn technique was getting it up to a temperature that was sufficiently hot. Once hot enough, the wood softened quickly. A quick scrape and another half an hour of burning enabled the removal of the next layer, and so on. This was found to be a very effective way of hollowing out the boat. Although it needed constant monitoring, it was just as efficient—if not more so in some ways—than the exclusive use of bronze axes and adzes.

Figure 7. Volunteer Aidan Phillips monitoring the burning of the log. photo credit Rockingham Forest Trust.

Participants soon realised that the intermittent nature of the volunteer days meant that the wood often got very wet and was difficult to relight, having had to be fully extinguished at the end of each session. The end conclusion was that the burning would have been more effective if the fire had stayed lit and at the right temperature until the whole of the hollowing out process was complete. They also deduced that having a lit fire over a longer period of time would naturally have had other practical uses as well, such as keeping warm and food. The volunteers utilised this on the build weekends, and many BBQs were had!

The work continued until Winter 2023, when the boats were wrapped to protect them against freezing temperatures. It was important not to let ice infiltrate the wood as this could cause damage that would be difficult to repair. The volunteers spent the winter months working on their paddles, basing their designs on Stone Age paddles found in Denmark (Andersen, 2018). In early Spring 2024, and the boat build re-started again as the temperatures warmed. The volunteers returned for weekly sessions and boat build weekends working on finessing the shape of the boats.

two of the vessels had faithfully followed many of the Must Farm boat designs insofar as they were open ended and had required transom boards for their creation. In total, the build of the three log boats took just over 800 hours— a volunteering feat in itself!

Figure 8. The volunteers adding the finishing touches to the boats. photo credit Emma Jones / Ancient Craft.

The Launch

On 21st July 2024, against the backdrop of the beautiful ‘Solstice Lake’, the Big Bronze Age Boat Launch commenced. The event was a celebration of the Boat Build project, but also a celebration of the rich history of the site with visitors enjoying historical foods, ancient textiles and a display from Cambridgeshire Archaeological Unit about Must Farm – “Britain’s Pompeii”.

The two main log boats were lashed together with a panel woven of willow branches which formed a deck (much like modern catamarans) to add stability and load capacity. The transom boards were fitted and sealed in place with clay from the lakebed. The volunteers worked on the finishing touches throughout the day and were dressed in replica Bronze Age clothing as they readied themselves and the vessels. See Figure 8. As the log boats were launched into the lake the crowd cheered, and it was a magical moment for all the team. See Figure 9.

Figure 9. Paddles raised in celebration as the boats launch onto the lake. photo credit Emma Jones / Ancient Craft.

Of particular interest was how the two transom boards would hold up. Although the volunteers had worked very hard to make sure they fitted tightly into the open stern slots, there was still some concern about how they would perform against the water pressure. But they held and not one ball of clay was required to plug any leaks! The boats moved on the water relatively quickly for paddle propelled vessels. The larger paddles made for much more accurate steering, and even the catamaran style log boats felt light and easy to maneuver in the water.

It was a real insight into crafting the boats and how they could have been used on the ancient riverways to travel and trade. See Figure 10. Dr James Dilley says

“The Bronze Age boat build was a special project for a variety of reasons including broad engagement with different demographics and its focus on inclusivity - a key avenue for the future of all archaeological projects. The Stanwick Lakes team have excelled in facilitating a project that also managed to generate archaeological data that proved useful to archaeologists from Cambridge Archaeological Unit on the back of their work on the late Bronze Age pile dwelling settlement of Must Farm. The success of this project is especially visible through its legacy - as well as enthusing a large audience who have engaged with a variety of archaeological resources, the build team have already set their sights on the next step as they 'build' towards bigger projects at Stanwick Lakes.”

Figure 10. Boat build volunteers celebrate the successful launch. photo credit Kerry Aspinwall / RF Trust.

The Big Bronze Age Boat build exceeded its objectives and all expectations set at the beginning of the project – raising the profile of heritage, increasing volunteer involvement, skills development in ancient crafts and engaging people in archaeology! We are indescribably pleased and energized.

So, what next? The Big Bronze Age Boat Build is just the start of our heritage journey at Stanwick Lakes. We are looking forward to continuing this exciting exploration of our ancient and revered landscape in future projects!

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Project Overview

A New Method for Heritage Monitoring: EAMENA Machine Learning Automated Change Detection Tool

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The Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa ([EAMENA](#)) project is a collaborative initiative between the Universities of Oxford, Leicester and Durham, funded by Arcadia. This project began in 2015 with the main objectives of recording, documenting and monitoring heritage sites across the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region (Bewley et al., 2016, Zerbini, 2018).

At EAMENA, we work closely with our local partners from the MENA region: in particular, the relevant heritage authorities in each of the countries where we work. A series of grants from the British Council's Cultural Protection Fund have enabled us to provide training in remote sensing methods and technical support to our local partners for the documentation and assessment of heritage across the MENA region. Using a combination of remote sensing methods, the digitisation of archival records, and fieldwork, the project has documented over 200,000 heritage sites across the MENA region, encompassing all kinds of heritage, from the Palaeolithic to Early Modern periods, with many more yet to be documented.

Figure 11. EAMENA Database. Photo by Julia Nikolaus, ©EAMENA.

These archaeological records are deposited in the EAMENA database, which is built on the open-source Arches software and hosted at the University of Oxford. See Figure 11. We share this database

with our sister project, the Maritime Endangered Archaeology (MarEA) project. Different levels of access to the EAMENA database are available for heritage professionals, researchers, students, or members of the general public, and the database is available in both English and Arabic. Registration to access the EAMENA database is available [online](#) (Oxford and Southampton, 2024).

The enormous number of sites recorded in the database presents significant challenges in monitoring all these sites. To help us in this task, the EAMENA project has developed a number of automated remote sensing tools that can easily and rapidly assess and monitor the condition of heritage sites over time.

The first EAMENA Automated Change Detection (ACD) methodology and workflow was published in 2020 and employs the Google Earth Engine platform to compare pixel values across two Sentinel-2 satellite image composites (Rayne et al., 2020). The script determines where changes have occurred within the user-defined buffer zones of sites of interest and identifies sites with significant change based on the user-defined change threshold. This tool provides a simple and rapid way to determine whether any changes have occurred within the vicinity of an archaeological site during a given time period.

However, this method provides only a binary result which shows areas of change or no change. It does not provide information on the type of change which has occurred, the time period during which the change was detected, or whether said change is ongoing. Therefore, the Leicester EAMENA team developed a new method of the ACD using Machine Learning methods which would also be able to provide answers to these questions.

EAMENA Machine Learning Automated Change Detection (EAMENA MLACD)

The EAMENA Machine Learning Automated Change Detection (EAMENA MLACD) is a novel tool that revolutionizes the detection and monitoring of threats to archaeological sites by enabling heritage professionals to fully utilize the latest advancements in remote sensing technologies and cloud computing services (Mahmoud et al., 2024). The EAMENA MLACD requires basic knowledge of remote sensing and GIS, particularly in image classification and the collection of training samples for training the supervised machine learning model.

The method uses the JavaScript programming language and leverages the cloud computing service of [Google Earth Engine](#). It applies machine learning algorithms (i.e., Random Forest) to process time series of satellite images (i.e., Sentinel-2) and generate land classification maps. By comparing the land classification maps, this method effectively detects changes and threats to archaeological sites over time. It determines whether a change has occurred, provides detailed information on the type of change or threat (e.g., urbanization, flooding, vegetation expansion, earth disturbance), specifies the time period when the change was detected and also indicates whether the change is ongoing.

The tool implementation framework includes three main stages:

Defining variables: This stage involves determining the extent of the study area, identifying the heritage sites under investigation and selecting the training samples that will be used to train the machine learning model for supervised classification. It also includes setting the visualization parameters for automating the output of results and defining a location (P) for more in-depth change analysis at one particular point or area of interest.

Image classification and analysis: In this stage, supervised classification identifies pixels corresponding to each land cover class (as defined in the variables and input step) using the training dataset.

Identification of disturbances and threats: In this stage, the user is able to generate outputs which identify the types and dates of disturbances and threats to heritage sites detected by the script.

The EAMENA MLACD automatically generates various visual and statistical outputs. These include land cover classification maps that show representations of different land cover types, a binary change map and change class map that indicate areas of change within the study area and an animated GIF map that displays changes over the period of interest. It also generates time series analysis charts that show changes in the proportions of each land cover class and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) over time for the entire study area and also for the specific user-defined locations. Additionally, it produces histograms that provide the relative frequency of each change class within the site buffer zones, allowing users to visualize specific changes at individual sites. The tool also generates downloadable data files to allow for further analysis or validation in GIS software. Finally, it produces accuracy data (such as confusion matrices) to assess the success of the analysis and allows the user to identify where they may need to refine their parameters or training samples for better results (Mahmoud et al., 2024).

A user interface has also been developed for the EAMENA MLACD to allow users with limited coding experience to more easily interact with the framework. The interface enables users to define certain variables, such as the dates for the period of study and the buffer distance for the heritage sites under investigation by entering them into the user-friendly format. See Figure 12.

Figure 12. EAMENA Machine Learning Automated Change Detection User Interface.

In order to help new users, we have developed training documentation that showcases the functionality of the tool and provides guidance on how to use it. The code and comprehensive step-

by-step instructions for adapting and implementing the EAMENA MLACD, available in both English and Arabic, can be accessed on the [EAMENA GitHub repository](#).

Monitoring Heritage in Bani Walid using EAMENA MLACD

The EAMENA MLACD has been implemented to detect changes and threats to archaeological sites in the area of Bani Walid, a city located in northwest Libya. More than 200 heritage sites dating from the Roman to Medieval and Early Modern periods, include farms buildings, settlements and field systems were recorded and analysed using the EAMENA MLACD method. See Figure 13.

Figure 13. Archaeological sites of Bani Walid, northwest Libya. The sites located within the modern town are significantly endangered due to severe urban expansion activities.

The results of the EAMENA MLACD analysis identified several issues affecting the heritage sites of Bani Walid, such as urbanization, vegetation expansion, quarrying and bulldozing activities. For example, Figure 14 illustrates areas of urbanization identified by the MLACD and the classification time series change results at site EAMENA-0087039, showing the construction of two buildings within the buffer zone of the site. Archived images show that this part of the site was classified as bare land in 2013; however, construction activity and bulldozing work began in 2016 and were completed sometime between 2019 and 2021. See Figure 14, a-e. Although most of the construction activity took place before the period under investigation by the EAMENA MLACD (2019-2023), the threat of urbanization was still identified and detected by the MLACD. This is evident from the pixel change map, which shows some pixels classified as urban within the site premises. See Figure 14, g.

Figure 14. Urbanization detected at site EAMENA-0087039, Bani Walid. The high-resolution archive images from Google Earth (a)-(e) show construction activity between 2013 and 2022. This part of the site was classified as bare land until construction activity began in 2016 and was completed between 2019 and 2021. Another segment (f) is the classification change map showing urban pixels in red, and (g) is the classification time series at location (P).

The changes detected by the MLACD at the archaeological sites of Bani Walid were validated during a fieldwork survey conducted in February 2024 by a team of heritage professionals from the Libyan Department of Antiquities. The fieldwork demonstrated that the tool performed well in identifying changes and threats. However, the fieldwork also documented additional threats, such as trash dumping and looting, which were not detected by the MLACD (Mahmoud et al., 2024). See Figure 15. This limitation is due to the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 images (10 meters per pixel) used in the MLACD, which makes identifying smaller threats more difficult. Sentinel-2 imagery is used because it is available free and open-access, but it is possible to adapt the script to use higher spatial resolution images which would better enable the detection of smaller scale threats like these.

Figure 15. Fieldwork survey documenting threats to heritage sites in Bani Walid. (a) well preserved fortified farm building; (b) active construction activity; (c) vegetation growth; (d) trash dumping and (e) looting pit. Photos by Muftah Ahmed and Nader El-Kanadi.

Dissemination and Significance of the EAMENA MLACD Tool

The EAMENA MLACD tool has been developed and made available online as an open-access resource to enable heritage professionals to detect threats and rapidly monitor heritage sites. Supported by the Cultural Protection Fund, the EAMENA project has now trained over twenty heritage professionals from Libya and Algeria on how to utilize the EAMENA MLACD tool for heritage monitoring in their respective countries. Additionally, we have trained eight heritage researchers from the UK who work in the MENA region on how to use the EAMENA MLACD to support them in their heritage monitoring studies.

The EAMENA MLACD tool is currently integrated and widely used by multiple offices of the Department of Antiquities of Libya as one of their heritage monitoring tools. Additional training programs are scheduled to further promote the EAMENA MLACD as a powerful tool for heritage monitoring and preservation.

The EAMENA MLACD also has broader applications beyond monitoring heritage sites, such as in the fields of earth observation and environmental monitoring. This is primarily due to its initial development for the time series land cover classification, which can be used to investigate various phenomena such as deforestation monitoring, coastal erosion, wildfires, and flood assessments.

Funding

The EAMENA project is funded by [Arcadia](#). The work presented here has also been generously supported by a grant from the British Council and DCMS funded Cultural Protection Fund. At the University of Leicester (where the majority of the MLACD work was undertaken) the EAMENA project also sits within and is supported by the Centre for Endangered Archaeology and Heritage. The fieldwork survey in Bani Walid was funded through the Cultural Protection Fund and was carried out by teams of heritage professionals from the Libyan Department of Antiquities.

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Research Overview

Mobility and Social Integration of the Formerly Enslaved in the Ancient Greek World

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The ancient Greek world was famously a world on the move. The communities of the eastern Mediterranean depended on each other for the necessities of life, including human resources. Funerary inscriptions from practically all ancient Greek city-states testify to the constant movement and exchange of people between cities and to the presence of considerable migrant communities.

In 2020, aided by a grant from Danish Council for Independent Research, I was able to put together a small international and interdisciplinary research team under the auspices of the project *‘Migrants and Membership Regimes’* to investigate how and under what circumstances migration shaped the lives of ancient Greek city-state communities. The free male migrant stands dominant in the epigraphic evidence (that is to say, those written records inscribed on stone); but the project set itself the challenge of examining how different attributes—gender, status, wealth, language—shaped the migrant experience and outcomes in the ancient Greek world.

One obvious (but also partly obscure) migration was that of enslaved individuals from the periphery of the Greek world into Greek cities. The exact scale of these migrations is debated, but it is generally agreed that slavery was a foundational institution for ancient Greek society. It touched every aspect of life: economic, social, religious, and political. Slavery’s social embeddedness presents a methodological problem. Slavery as an institution was never the object of the sustained interest of ancient writers, and only rarely do individual slaves emerge in the evidence. While they were always there in the background – always in the picture so to say – they were never the subject of focus.

Delphi and Corpus

That ubiquitous, but obscured presence finds a striking example at the sanctuary of the god Apollo in Delphi. The sanctuary—home to not only the famous oracle, but also to the Pythian Games, a quadrennial festival on par with that celebrated in Olympia—was a center of the ancient Greek world and a place of display for the Greek city-states. The so-called Sacred Way that meanders up the mountain, through the sanctuary, past Apollo’s temple and the monumental theatre to the hippodrome, is lined with the treasuries of the Greek cities. See Figure 16. The sanctuary housed the most precious and impressive gifts bestowed upon Apollo by the citizens of this or that city state, reminding all visitors of their surplus wealth and piety. Among these are monuments to royal families and monuments celebrating military victories.

Behind the display, the massive retaining wall turns out to be covered in writing. Said writing is not in continuous text, but in smoothed patches on the wall, each carrying a document, inscribed in tiny (about 1 cm tall) letters, relating to the freeing of one or more enslaved persons. See Figure 17. These inscriptions are a kind of deeds of sale attesting to the transfer of ownership of a person from a free person, usually a citizen of Delphi, to Apollo, the god of the sanctuary, who assumes ownership for the expressed purpose of setting said person free.

Figure 16. Tourists make their way up the Sacred Way in Delphi in the May heat of 2024.

If the lives of the enslaved and the lives of the formerly enslaved are often only poorly attested in our evidence, the point of transition from one state to another (manumission) is precisely the opposite. In addition to the manumission documents from Delphi, similar inscribed documents have been recovered from Lokris, Boiotia, Aitolia, Thessaly, Lakonia and Kalymnos. The total evidence amounts to several thousand documents. It would not be unreasonable to call manumission one of the most well-attested social events of the ancient Greek world (though death, of course, takes the prize).

Figure 17. Inscribed retaining wall along the Sacred Way and the Treasury of the Athenians.

That fact translates into a curious methodological and practical problem. Firstly, the study of freed persons' mobility depends almost entirely on the records that granted this status, which attest mainly to the assumptions and desires of the slave-owners, and only indirectly to the experiences of the freed through whatever conclusions slave owners drew from interacting with their former slaves. Secondly, the material evidence is vast, uneven, and unwieldy.

These problems multiply when comparing inscriptions across sites (and thereby also across time and legal and social conditions). But even within the site of Delphi, gaining a full view of the evidence is not an easy task. The recent publication of *Corpus des inscriptions de Delphes* V.1 (2020) and V.2 (2023) by Dominique Mulliez, collects and reedit the manumission documents inscribed at Delphi. But Mulliez' edition does a lot more than correct our counting. It rests on a new and careful reading, aided, of course, by the published observations of many brilliant epigraphers that read the inscriptions. The result is that many of the texts are more reliable. In other words, the publication of these two volumes is a game changer for the study of ancient slavery, manumission, freed persons, and their mobility.

The Documents

A total of 1272 documents are preserved from c. 200 BCE to 50 CE. The documents specify the seller by name, the price and the conditions of the sale, but also record basic information regarding the person being sold. Presumably this was in conformity with regular deeds of sale: the name, gender and origin of the person in question.

Names clearly served to distinguish one slave from another. But they also betray the owners' fascination with the exotic (some slaves were given foreign names that did not match their origin) or with the virtues that Greek slaveowners hoped to find or instill in their unfree laborers: we find sobriquets like 'Pleasant' (Hedeia, *CID V.1 37*), 'Moderate' (Sophrona, *CID V.1 54*), and 'Remaining' (Paramona, *CID V.1 133*), to name only a few. If the giving of such names reflected a hope that the enslaved would conform, they may also concomitantly intimate that the enslaved themselves felt or acted quite the opposite.

Gender and origin also helped identify slaves and were clearly important properties. Work—which included care work—in the ancient Greek household was gendered, and the high proportion of women among the manumitted (some 65%) is usually explained by owners' affection for their caregiving slaves, who were disproportionately female. The role of gender in shaping the institution of slavery, the experience of being enslaved and eventual outcomes for the unfree, is an important emerging field of inquiry, and the subject of a forthcoming volume edited by Andrew Lepke, Lene Rubinstein and Claire Taylor. The volume explores, among other things, the dynamics of reproduction and reproductive strategies (D. Kamen), and points (C. Taylor) to the gendered nature of the transaction: female slaves were overwhelmingly freed by female owners.

The documents also make plain that slavery and migration were intrinsically linked. At least 40% of the enslaved in Delphi had been extracted—and in all likelihood forcibly so—from their homes and found themselves in a foreign land with strange customs and an unfamiliar language (an Aristotelian treatise on household management counsels the purchase of slaves with different origins, in order that the enslaved members of the house do not share a language unknown to their masters). That proportion, however, likely reflects a preference for locally-born slaves for care work, that is for enslaved persons whose native (and perhaps only) language was Greek and who had no personal recollection of a life of freedom. But the local supply clearly did not meet the demand. In a forthcoming article co-authored with David Lewis (Edinburgh), I explore the evidence from Delphi with similar manumission documents from Locris and the funerary record of Rhodes to trace out the patterns of slave imports to these places. We are able to trace the expansion of slaving zones along the periphery of the Greek world, as that world itself expanded over the course of the Hellenistic period, i.e., during the three centuries that followed the conquests of Alexander the Great. Furthermore, there is good evidence that gender and origin intersected in certain preferences. Male slaves from Cappadocia, for instance, and female slaves from Thrace, can be seen in the preferences of slave buyers in both Delphi and Rhodes.

Figure 18. Inscribed manumission documents.

The Delphic and other manumission documents are evidence that most (if not all) Greek cities were home to substantial populations of formerly enslaved persons. See Figure 18. One strain of my own research, which is shaping into a book, is concerned with documenting these lives and in particular post-enslavement mobility. In the Delphic documents, the abstract concept of freedom is glossed as “going where one wants, and doing as one pleases”, indicating that freedom was first and foremost understood as the freedom of movement. A key issue, then, is the following: where did the formerly enslaved go when they were finally allowed to go where they wanted? The manumission documents provide a partial and heartbreaking answer: nowhere. About a third of the manumission documents include a so-called ‘paramone clause’, which stipulated that the freed person was required to remain with their owners—usually until the owner died—performing all of the same tasks and with the same obedience as they had as slaves. But what about those who were not required to stay?

I must pause to note that the evidence, such as it is, is incapable of recording the potential return of some former slaves to their home communities. However, there are indications that staying around was the dominant norm. In one case, a man from Achaia (in the Peloponnese) travelled to Delphi to free his slave and specified that he, the freed slave, could not under the terms of the agreement, set foot in Achaia ever again. The provision is unique and tickles the imagination (did this slave witness a crime?). More importantly, it lays bare the assumption that freed persons would be expected to want to remain in the same community as their former owners. There may have been attachments: for

example, family and especially children that remained enslaved, or there may have been fears of a life in the unknown. Certainly, the institutional protection for the newly freed encouraged sticking around.

In Delphi, citizens and magistrates witnessed and guaranteed the manumission and the laws of the city made the defense—even the violent defense—of a freed person’s freedom an unimpeachable action. Elsewhere in the Greek world the entire citizenry swore to protect the freedom of freed persons. But that very earnest commitment to respecting a manumission ended at the border of a city’s territory. That limitation was to an extent a reflection of the politically fragmented world of the ancient Greek city states. A closer look at the material suggests that the retention of a substantial pool of non-citizens with no better options on hand could work as a human resource buffer in times of need.

In any Greek city, social and political reproduction were almost always at a risk. Cities needed labour. Gods expected the usual sacrifices. But equally important was the fact that cities required citizens. They needed people for the defense of the city and for the running of institutions. The freed population represented a pool of human resources that could be tapped into in case of need. The latter part was important, in case of pressing need. In crises, members of the freed population could be enrolled as citizens. This was not necessarily uncontroversial. In a handful of manumission documents, owners give (or withhold) their consent for their former slaves to become enrolled in the citizenry, suggesting that owners had a say in whom could be tapped for citizenship. Such were only one type of provision found in the documents. Owners added what seems to be an endless list of idiosyncratic provisions to the Delphic manumission agreements. Perhaps this is evidence of the extreme prerogative of slave owners in organizing the social world of Hellenistic Delphi. Perhaps further studies of the documents will detect patterns that represent legal changes, in turn reflecting new common challenges to the community. The potential of this human resource is perhaps most clearly expressed at the private level: when families were in need of male heirs. In some cases, enslaved children were adopted (it is an easy assumption that their adoptive fathers were probably also their biological fathers) and freed women could be married into the ranks of the citizens.

Migration of the enslaved was, therefore, twofold and perhaps played out over generations. One individual’s extraction from the periphery of the Greek world could lead to sale in a community like Delphi. Under the right circumstances, this could eventually lead to migration through the orders of the city from slave, to freed person to citizen, with all the duties and privileges that citizenship entailed (including owning slaves of their own). What at the outset might look to be the stable and stale institutions of the Greek cities begins to look quite dynamic. The continuous trafficking of enslaved labour into ancient Greek cities provided an economic basis for those societies, but, by and by, that same workforce could be converted to plug the holes of the familial or social order whenever they occurred and for whatever reasons. Visit our project website ([here](#)) to learn more!

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Short Report

A new clay wheel fragment on a Vučedol site of Szilvás in Southeast Transdanubia (Hungary)

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This paper is intended to provide a brief introduction to information about a newly found wheel fragment (possibly connected to a wagon model) in the Vučedol site of Szilvás, Hungary. The find is exciting given the importance and attention paid to such 3rd millennium BC technological innovations by European prehistoric research. Over the course of their collaboration, Kiel University and the Janus Pannonius Museum organized a field campaign in Baranya County, southeast Transdanubia in March 2024. The main goal was to measure enclosure ditches and study how these ditches were related to prehistoric settlement structures with particular attention to the Late Neolithic period. We combined geomagnetic surveys and surface find-collecting activities in order to be able to study the spatial and temporal dimensions of these enclosed ditch sites. See Figure 19. Altogether, two Late Neolithic rondel sites (Zengővárkony and Vokány, both associated with the Lengyel Culture, c. 5th millennium BCE) and one Early Bronze Age site (at Szilvás-Ó-szeg) were studied during surveys south of Pécs during the spring of 2024. Here we present the first results from the Szilvás site, where some promising anomalies within the settlement structures and pottery material were discovered.

Szilvás-Ó-szeg site

The Szilvás site is registered in the site catalogue of the Hungarian Cultural Heritage Office (previous Kulturális Örökségvédelmi Hivatal, currently Forster Gyula Nemzeti Örökséggazdálkodási és Szolgáltatási Központ) and with Janus Pannonius Museum. It is situated to the south of the villages of Szőke and Szilvás on the southern edge of a Loess plateau closed by the Bosta Creek on the west and the Szilvás-mellékág stream to the east. The entire east bank of the Loess plateau runs into the Szilvás-mellékág stream. The geomagnetic plan measured in 2024 covered only a part of the site, as vegetation prevented survey of the western- and the southernmost parts of the site. See Figure 20. On the basis of the aerial and satellite images as well as previous surface finds, the site can be dated to the Early Bronze Age (3rd millennium BCE). The site has been known since 2007 when the first aerial archaeological prospection was carried out by Gábor Bertók. At that time, an enclosed area with several ditch-like anomalies was observed. In 2008 and 2009, colleagues from Janos Pannonius Museum field walked at the site and identified Neolithic, as well as Early and Late Bronze Age pottery sherds (Bertók et al. 2014, 118–119).

Figure 19. Surface collection and geomagnetic prospection were utilized during the 2024 field survey. Photo © Fynn Wilkes, used here with permission.

Figure 20. The location of the site at Szilvás relative to the Baranya region and Hungarian borders.

Figure 21. The visibility of the Szilvás site and the area which was geomagnetically prospected projected on Google Satellite Hybrid Imagery (EPSG:3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator). Image © Kiel University.

Altogether, five ditches are visible from the area prospected geomagnetically. To the north, two more or less parallel linear ditches run in a southwest-northeast direction which are approximately 20-30 meters apart. The linear ditches measure 5-6 meters. The eastern ends of these anomalies are outside the prospected area and are now lost due to erosion. Two ditches were detected in the middle of the surveyed area. The northern ditch forms what is almost a straight line in a northwest-southeast direction, and the southern one has the same orientation, but is curved. A gate-like structure is visible on the eastern parts of the ditches. These are five and six meters wide, respectively. The ditches in this area are widened by the gate-like constructions, displayed in 'L'-shaped features facing the centre. These ditches are visible over a distance of about 200 meters. The southernmost ditch is the widest one (10-13 m) and stretches for over 345 meters in the measured area. Based on its circular or oval shape, one could expect a ditch which may originally have measured up to 520 m, thereby enclosing an area of 10.3 hectares.

On the northwest part of this ditch, one gate-like structure is identifiable. This created a 10-meter-wide free space as an earth bridge for entering the inner part of the ditch system. The western part of this gate-like structure has an 'L'-shaped wider part, but the other side of the ditch also displays a thicker area as well. See Figure 21. The empty space is related to this 'L-shaped' gate-like structure, as this 20-meter-wide area does not show any detectable anomalies, either inside or outside of the circular ditch. The situation appears as if the empty space may have been a walkway or road used to

enter the ditch. A similar 5-10-meter-wide space is observable in the case of the double middle ditches between the two smaller gates. Free spaces are visible along the inner side of the circular and curved double ditches. These could be interpreted as places for ramparts. See Figure 22. Ditch-rampart earth-wood constructions have been well-known for making an enclosure more prominent since the Late Neolithic times across all prehistoric periods. The northernmost southwest-northeast-oriented double ditches show free spaces as well. The relation of these northernmost two ditches to the circular ditch system is still unclear, though further measurement on the western part of the site could help shed light on this question.

Figure 22. Interpretative plan of the magnetic survey at Szilvás. Image © Kiel University.

The archaeological materials collected from the surface consist of mostly pottery, but also one spindle whorl and several chipped, polished and ground stones. The surface pottery finds can be associated with the Late Copper Age-Early Bronze Age Vučedol pottery style which is dated 3000/2900-2500/2400 cal BCE (Durman et al. 1989; Benkö et al. 1989; Bulatović et al. 2017; Bulatović et al. 2020). See Figure 23. The most characteristic diagnostic pottery sherds from the collected surface assemblage include bowl fragments with interior decorations made of white encrusted motives, which are typical for the Vučedol pottery style.

Figure 23. Selection of white incrustrated Vučedol pottery style from the Szilvás site. Image © Kiel University.

The most prominent piece of the surface collection is undoubtedly a clay wheel fragment that was discovered between the circular and curved ditches in the area of the potential building structures. See Figure 24. The wheel fragment is 10 centimetres in diameter. The axis of the wheel is 7 cm long, and the perforation of the axis is 15 mm in diameter. The surface of the wheel fragment is relatively smooth, though some minor cracks are visible. Based on the dimension of the wheel fragment, we assume that this was part of a bigger wagon model construction which has many parallels from the Early Bronze Age period in the Carpathian Basin.

Figure 24. Clay wheel fragment of the possible wagon model at Szilvás. Image © Kiel University.

A close parallel find is known from the Early Bronze Age Börzönce-Temetői-dűlő site in Zala County, where a wagon model is known with three identical solid wheels with perforations for an axle (Bondár 1992; Bondár 2012). See Figure 25. The reconstruction drawing of the Börzönce wagon model suggests a representation of a simple, unadorned wooden cart, with solid wooden wheels on an axle. Likewise, the other wagon models presented in Figure 25 represent solid wheels that have a perforation in the middle. Wheels with perforations in the middle and their conical shape indicated wheels rotating around the axle. This kind of representation style is associated with the Early and Middle Bronze Age wagon models in Carpathian Basin contexts (Bóna 1960; Bondár 2012; Boroffka 2004; Maran 2004).

Figure 25. Some wheel and wagon models from the Bronze Age context in Hungary (source of the images: Börzönce (Somogyvár-Vinkovci culture, EBA): Bondár 1992, 123, Fig. 5.; Pocsaj (Ottomány culture, EBA-MBA): © Déri Museum, photographer Ákos Jurás; Vésztő (Gyulavarsánd culture, EBA-MBA): Bondár 2012, 61, Fig.21.3, after (Kovács 1994, 76, Fig.38); Encs (Füzesabony culture, EBA-MBA): (Mengyán et al. 2023, 208, Fig.7); Berettyószentmárton (Gyulavarsánd culture, EBA-MBA): Bondár 2012, 61, Fig.21.4, after (Bóna 1994), Cat. no. 330.

The solid clay wheel fragment and its clay tunnel-like structure around the perforation allows us to suggest that this find from the Szilvás site could be part of an Early Bronze Age wagon model in spite of the fact that the wagon box was not discovered. Although the number of Bronze Age wagon models and wheels is numerous in the Carpathian Basin, only a few finds have been known from Transdanubia. This makes the Szilvás find important. The potential ditch-rampart structure of the

settlement of Szilvás and the location on the elevated plateau allows us to interpret the site as a likely fortification. Taking into account the diagnostic pottery sherds, it is plausible that the site may have been a Vučedol fortified settlement. Our work, which so far has only consisted of surface find collection and geomagnetic prospection, has not yet been able to answer 1) how the northern ditches related to the entire settlement structure, or 2) whether some of the empty spaces between the dense distribution of pit-like anomalies indicate potential above-ground buildings. Undoubtedly, continuing geomagnetic prospection on the western part of the site, small-scale excavations, coring and C14 dating will be important for further research on what has already shown to be a promising site indeed.

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Insight

CifA – a Professional Home for Archaeologists in the UK: A new focus for the UK's professional institute

Nathan Baker

Chartered Institute for Archaeologists - UK

Archaeology is a vibrant, exciting and energising discipline which, for anyone who has an interest in history, place and community, provides a great opportunity to shape the future by learning from the past. Every day the stories archaeologists tell through the finds, the artefacts and the settlements inspire people to look at the world around them in a different way and to craft their own story of how their local community has evolved. Whether it be in the local news, on national television or international media, the influence of archaeology on society is seen and felt by millions of people. That reach and the positive impact it has is something the sector should be rightly proud of and one which, at the UK's Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (CifA), we will celebrate and build upon.

On getting involved with archaeology a newcomer sees a sector that has many facets, all focused on protecting heritage for the good of society. This common purpose, of delivering societal value by promoting the 'art and science' of archaeology is a strong one, and one that resonates with the other industries and sectors with which archaeologists of all types work. As one of those newcomers, I have been impressed with the passion people have. It is refreshing to see so many loving the career they have chosen. It is why the public are drawn to what archaeologists all do – archaeologists bring the past to life in exciting ways and make the lessons identified relevant to today.

As the UK's professional home, CifA will be reflecting on our contribution to that common purpose, supporting our passion and how it links to the Institute's Charter objectives. I am keen that our focus as an Institute becomes one around learning. A place where those who have enthusiasm for archaeology come together, share their knowledge and expertise, help each other to continually improve, inspire the next generation to join the sector and encourage policy and decision makers to keep archaeology at the heart of community development. By focusing on being relevant and delivering impact, we will place archaeologists, the members, at the heart of the Institute.

The opportunities for archaeology are vast: from the exploitation of technology to understand the sites we work on better, to connecting our modern communities with the communities of the past and telling rich stories about human progress. Aligning our work to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDG) will clearly demonstrate to all the value archaeology delivers.

As we look to the future, CifA has a central role to play in championing the value the sector brings to society. We will seek, at every opportunity, to demonstrate that archaeology and archaeologists are highly relevant in the modern world and deliver positive impact for society. Through the membership, archaeology connects the past to the future by telling inspiring stories of how our ancestors lived and thrived. Collectively, we are able to provide context to the way we live today and give insight into how we might, effectively, live tomorrow.

Insight

ICOMOS International Charter for Cultural Heritage Tourism (2022): A New Paradigm for Archaeologists and Heritage Professionals

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ICOMOS
international cultural tourism committee

The *ICOMOS International Charter for Cultural Heritage Tourism (2022): Reinforcing cultural heritage protection and community resilience through responsible and sustainable tourism management*, was adopted at the ICOMOS General Assembly in Bangkok in October 2022. The Charter marks a significant evolution in cultural heritage management by integrating principles of sustainability, community resilience and ethical participative governance in management. The *ICOMOS International Cultural Tourism Committee (ICTC)*—established in 1969—was among the international earliest scientific committees of ICOMOS and Charter represents a development from earlier ICOMOS charters (1976 and 1999) on cultural tourism (<https://www.icomosictc.org/>).

Figure 26. Members of ICOMOS ICTC at the ICOMOS General Assembly in Bangkok where the new Charter was approved. From left to right: Faisal Abd Rahman, Hila Steinmetz, Sofia Fonseca, Ivan Henares, Célia Martinez, Fergus MacLaren, Richard Mackay and Pierre-François Toulze. Photo © ICOMOS- ICTC.

The ICTC is a global network of academics and professionals from cultural heritage, conservation and tourism that offers a framework for safeguarding cultural heritage while promoting responsible and sustainable tourism. The ICTC plays a pivotal role in research and policy development, advising for organizations including UNESCO, UNWTO and IUCN, while addressing the growing tensions between tourism development (and its use of cultural heritage resources) and the protection and conservation of cultural heritage, especially at UNESCO World Heritage sites. See Figure 26.

The Charter has already been translated into seven languages (English, French, Spanish, Italian, Chinese, Arabic, and Danish), with additional translations in progress for Slovenian, Portuguese, German, Japanese, and Hindi. The Charter reshapes how tourism and heritage professionals—including archaeologists—can best engage with cultural heritage and is built on seven guiding principles that seek to:

1. place cultural heritage protection and conservation at the centre of responsible cultural tourism planning and management
2. manage tourism at cultural heritage places through management plans informed by monitoring, carrying capacity and other planning instruments
3. enhance public awareness and visitor experience through sensitive interpretation and presentation of cultural heritage
4. recognize and reinforce the rights of communities, Indigenous Peoples and traditional owners by including access and engagement in participatory governance of the cultural and natural heritage commons used in tourism
5. raise awareness and reinforce cooperation for cultural heritage conservation among all stakeholders involved in tourism
6. increase the resilience of communities and cultural heritage through capacity development, risk assessment, strategic planning and adaptive management
7. integrate climate action and sustainability measures in the management of cultural tourism and cultural heritage

For archaeologists, these principles provide a robust framework for addressing the current challenges for heritage preservation and the management of tourism in a rapidly changing world. The Charter positions cultural heritage not only as a set of physical sites and tourist destinations but as ‘commons’, meaning a shared resource (Garret, 1968; Ostrom, 1990) that is a vital socio-cultural resource requiring participative governance so that it can contribute to social cohesion and resilience, economic stability and environmental sustainability.

A Rights-Based, People-Centered Approach

One of the key innovations of the Charter is its people-centered and rights-based approach. Cultural heritage is no longer viewed solely as a set of monuments, sites and artefacts to be preserved, but as a living entity that embodies the cultural identity, values and traditions of local host communities. The Charter emphasizes that heritage places must be managed with deep respect for the communities concerned, including the rights of Indigenous Peoples and traditional owners. This approach seeks to move away from the extractive economic model of tourism and top-down methods of heritage

preservation and calls for participatory governance in which communities are active stewards of their own heritage.

For archaeologists, this shift underscores the importance of engaging with local stakeholders throughout the lifecycle of archaeological projects. Whether working on excavations, conservation, management or heritage interpretation, it is crucial to ensure that the voices and concerns of local communities and Indigenous Peoples are heard and respected. Archaeologists are now encouraged to collaborate with these groups and to integrate traditional knowledge and cultural practices into heritage management plans.

Heritage as a Resource for Community Resilience

Another critical aspect of the Charter is its focus on the need to use heritage as a resource for building community resilience against the increasing effects of climate change, environmental degradation, and mass tourism, all of which threaten cultural heritage sites. The Charter recognizes the vulnerability of tourism-dependent communities, particularly in the face of over-tourism and the commodification of cultural practices. It advocates for a balanced approach to tourism that avoids exploitation and instead promotes sustainable, respectful engagement with heritage.

For archaeologists, this means reassessing how archaeological sites are presented to the public and considering the long-term impacts of tourism on these locations. Archaeologists must work hand-in-hand with local heritage managers, communities and tourism professionals to develop management strategies that not only protect heritage, but also foster social cohesion and economic benefit-sharing for host communities.

Aligning with Global Sustainability Goals

In line with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—particularly Target 11.4, which focuses on safeguarding the world’s cultural and natural heritage—the Charter calls for a recalibration of tourism strategies. Archaeologists are now urged to embed sustainability measures into their heritage projects, ensuring that tourism management aligns with broader environmental and social objectives. This involves assessing the carrying capacity of heritage sites, conducting environmental and heritage impact assessments and employing adaptive management techniques that can respond to the changing conditions of the site and its surrounding community.

In practical terms, archaeologists need to collaborate with environmental scientists, urban planners, and local authorities to incorporate sustainability into the long-term interdisciplinary planning of heritage sites. By adopting these approaches, archaeologists can ensure that the cultural and natural environments are preserved not only for visitors today, but for future generations as well.

Addressing the Climate Emergency

Perhaps the most urgent aspect of the Charter is its emphasis on climate action and adaptation. The climate crisis poses a significant threat to cultural heritage with rising sea levels, extreme weather events and changing ecosystems jeopardizing the integrity of many archaeological sites. The Charter highlights the need for immediate and proactive measures to protect heritage in the face of these

challenges. For the archaeological community, this means integrating climate resilience strategies into heritage management plans and actively working to reduce the carbon footprint associated with heritage tourism.

This call to action is not only a professional responsibility, but a moral imperative. Archaeologists, along with other heritage managers and tourism professionals, are now tasked with ensuring that heritage sites contribute to broader climate action initiatives. This includes implementing green technologies in site management, promoting eco-friendly visitor experiences (Smith, 2023; CBD, 2021) and advocating for policies that support the preservation of heritage in a rapidly changing environment.

Conclusion

The *ICOMOS International Charter for Cultural Heritage Tourism (2022)* offers a comprehensive, forward-looking guide for archaeologists and heritage professionals. By embracing a people-centered, rights-based approach to heritage management, archaeologists can contribute to the protection and sustainable use of cultural resources while fostering resilience within local communities. The 2022 Charter also challenges archaeologists to integrate sustainability and climate action into their work, ensuring that cultural heritage continues to inspire and educate future generations in a way that respects both the past and the planet. As we move forward, archaeologists have the opportunity to lead in the implementation of these principles by using their unique expertise to ensure that cultural heritage remains a source of pride, knowledge and resilience for all.

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Insight

Learning the Art of Inquiry with generative AI: A Case Study in Anthropological Research

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Introduction

After more than fifty years as an anthropologist, I have learned that the art of asking precise, meaningful questions is critical to effective research. While inquiry has always been at the heart of my work, I recently introduced a new tool—generative AI—into my research process, initially with some skepticism. My focus this past year has been on Housepit 54 (HP 54) at the Bridge River site, about 250 kilometers northeast of Vancouver, British Columbia. It has been excavated and extensively reported on by Anna Marie Prentiss, Regents Professor of Anthropology at the University of Montana (Prentiss 2017, 2022). My goal was to refine my understanding of the emergence of social inequality. To my surprise, generative AI became an intellectual tool that helped me ask better questions and expand my inquiry in new directions. In this essay, I explore the role of generative AI in enhancing anthropological research and discuss how my effectiveness as a researcher depends on building and using a broad and comprehensive generative AI knowledge base for inquiry.

Clarifying Thought Processes

I chose the ChatGPT-4 program (OpenAI 2024) for my initial introduction to the use of generative AI. I soon discovered that the effectiveness of my inquiries depends on crafting precise and well-structured prompts. See Figure 27. When I posed broad questions such as “What does the archaeological evidence from HP 54 reveal about social inequality?”, the responses were informative but not groundbreaking. Refining my prompt to “How does the spatial organization within HP 54 reflect household segmentation, and what implications does this have for understanding wealth differentiation in the Mid-Fraser Canyon?”, yielded a more insightful answer. This experience showed that generative AI does not substitute for expertise—it responds to it. By framing more specific questions, I was able to guide the AI tool toward discussions that aligned with the depth of my research.

Figure 27. A ‘screen shot’ of a prompt that establishes authority, defines theoretical perspectives, and asks for a description and explanations of the culture history evidenced at House Pit 54 of the Bridge River site. It also specifies the audience’s background.

The iterative process of refining questions revealed the importance of breaking complex topics into smaller components. This was particularly useful in integrating theories from B.F. Skinner, Paul Colinvaux, and Albert Spaulding. Generative AI assisted me in structuring these theoretical frameworks into manageable parts, making it easier to explore connections between behavioral psychology, population ecology, and archaeological data. Clarifying my questions through interaction with generative AI sharpened my thought processes and made my inquiries more focused and effective.

The Role of a Comprehensive Knowledge Base

A key insight from my work with generative AI is that the quality of the responses I receive depends heavily on the breadth and depth of the knowledge I bring to the inquiry. When exploring social inequality at HP 54, I drew on decades of anthropological research, including studies on household

segmentation, resource management, and social hierarchy. This comprehensive background enabled me to craft prompts that were grounded in context and aligned with ongoing scholarly discussions. For example, when I asked “How does HP 54’s spatial organization compare to other relatively close pit house villages like Keatley Creek?”, I was able to frame the question in a way that connected specific architectural elements to regional trends in the Pacific Northwest.

Without this foundation, my prompts would likely have been too vague to yield meaningful insights. Generative AI relies on the quality of input to generate useful responses. It does not introduce new data or ideas independently; rather, it synthesizes information in response to the specific directions provided by the researcher. Building a strong knowledge base allowed me to engage more deeply with the AI tool, ensuring that the questions I posed were both relevant and insightful. The more comprehensive my understanding of the topic, the more effectively I could leverage AI as a tool for intellectual exploration.

Cross-Disciplinary Thinking and Synthesis

Generative AI has proven valuable in fostering cross-disciplinary thinking. My research draws on diverse theoretical frameworks—from behavioral psychology to ecological theory—and AI has helped me synthesize these perspectives in innovative ways. For example, when examining how HP 54’s spatial layout reflects social segmentation, generative AI prompted me to consider not just material constraints but also behavioral strategies that influence household organization. This interdisciplinary approach expanded the scope of my inquiry, allowing me to explore connections I might not have initially considered.

Generative AI also facilitated regional comparisons. In response to my prompt “How do social differentiation patterns at HP 54 compare to other pit house villages?”, it synthesized information across multiple case studies, revealing patterns in storage practices, access to resources, and household dynamics. This comparative analysis highlighted the importance of situating site-specific evidence within broader cultural and environmental contexts, deepening my understanding of HP 54’s role in the social history of the Pacific Northwest.

Promoting Iterative Questioning

Scientific inquiry is an iterative process, and my interactions with generative AI reflect this principle. Initial responses often lead to follow-up questions, creating a dynamic dialogue that encourages deeper exploration. For example, when I asked how artifact distribution at HP 54 reflects social segmentation, AI’s response suggested investigating storage spaces and wealth control. This prompted me to refine my questions further, exploring the relationship between communal and private storage and the emergence of social hierarchy.

This iterative exchange mirrors the scientific method, where each question generates new avenues for investigation. AI’s capacity to respond to evolving questions has enriched my research by revealing unexpected connections and guiding me toward new lines of inquiry. This process reinforces the value of patience and persistence in research, demonstrating that the best insights often emerge through multiple rounds of questioning.

Challenging Assumptions and Expanding Perspectives

Generative AI has also played a crucial role in challenging my assumptions and broadening my perspective. I explored the distribution of obsidian artifacts in southwestern Montana for another project. Initially, I focused on environmental factors. However, generative AI's responses encouraged me to also consider social dimensions—such as trade networks and symbolic meanings associated with obsidian use. This shift in perspective expanded my inquiry, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the interplay between environmental and cultural factors.

Similarly, generative AI prompted me to reconsider assumptions about household organization at HP 54. While initially, I interpreted household segmentation through existing models of social stratification, AI offered alternative perspectives, suggesting that storage practices and access to resources reflect both competitive and cooperative strategies. These insights helped me explore new dimensions of social inequality, deepening my understanding of how households function as dynamic units within broader socio-economic systems.

Integrating Theory into Inquiry

One of the most valuable aspects of using generative AI has been its ability to integrate theoretical perspectives into my research. I often framed prompts around specific models, such as evolutionary theories of social complexity or niche construction theory. For example, when I asked “How does HP 54's evidence align with models of social stratification in complex hunter-gatherer societies?”, generative AI connected architectural features with evolutionary theories of household segmentation and wealth accumulation. This dialogue between theory and evidence allowed me to test hypotheses and refine interpretations in ways that enhanced my understanding of the social dynamics at HP 54.

Generative AI's ability to synthesize theoretical frameworks with archaeological data has been instrumental in advancing my research. It provided a platform for exploring the dynamic interplay between cultural evolution and material practices, revealing new avenues for inquiry and helping me engage more deeply with complex theoretical models.

Conclusion: AI as an Intellectual Partner in Anthropological Inquiry

My initial skepticism about generative AI's value in academic research has evolved into an appreciation for its potential as an intellectual partner. Through interactions with generative AI, I have learned that the art of inquiry depends not just on asking questions but on asking the right questions—questions grounded in a robust knowledge base and framed in ways that invite meaningful exploration. Generative AI has enhanced my research by clarifying my thought processes, promoting interdisciplinary synthesis, encouraging iterative questioning, and challenging assumptions.

However, the effectiveness of generative AI does depend on the researcher's ability to provide a broad and comprehensive knowledge base. Without this foundation, prompts may lack the specificity needed to yield valuable insights. Generative AI does not replace expertise; it amplifies it by responding to well-informed questions and guiding researchers toward new perspectives.

In my study of HP 54 and the broader cultural history of the Pacific Northwest, generative AI has proven to be an essential tool for intellectual exploration. It has enriched my understanding of archaeological evidence, deepened my engagement with theoretical frameworks, and expanded the scope of my inquiry. By remaining the expert in this dialogue, I have been able to leverage generative AI's strengths while maintaining the rigor and critical thinking that define scholarly research.

In sum, generative AI has earned a place in my research toolkit, not as a replacement for expertise but as a valuable partner in the pursuit of knowledge. If we, as scholars, approach generative AI thoughtfully, we can harness its potential to enhance our inquiries, refine our interpretations, and navigate the complexities of anthropological research with greater depth and insight.

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Debate

A future for European professional institutes for archaeologists?

Peter Hinton

Independent

Our profession was frequently discussed in the 2024 Annual Meeting in Rome.

As ever, there was widespread confusion about what the word *profession* means, and it was often used to describe ‘all of us practising archaeology’ (the discipline), ‘all of us paid to do archaeology’ (the industry?), or ‘all of us with permission to undertake excavation’ (e.g., licence-holders) – rather than its true meaning: ‘those of us who have demonstrated competence in archaeology and who are accountable under an ethical code to put the public interest ahead of our own’.

The distinction matters. As the session organised by the Public Benefits of Archaeology Advisory Committee reinforced, archaeology is a powerful tool for the common good. The Valletta Convention and others recognise this, and all European countries that have ratified the Convention have implemented spatial planning policies to balance or align the benefits that development and archaeology bring to their citizens.

Unfortunately, we often fail to realise the full potential of archaeology. There is a tendency for archaeologists to market their services to developer clients as the efficient discharge of conditions (‘heritage decontamination’), telling us (and, worse still, their clients) that ‘developers aren’t interested in archaeology’. That statement is usually untested, and where it is true, it is because archaeologists have failed (or failed to try) to communicate the value of what we do. Shame on them!

The alternative approach, championed by the professional bodies in archaeology, is to market thoughtful research aimed both at maximising public benefit and at helping the developer use the history of their site create a distinctive, interesting and marketable (profitable) advantage over their real estate competitors.

The former approach, where the quality measure is as basic as ‘condition discharged’ or ‘condition not discharged’, turns what we do into an undifferentiated commodity. The issue with commoditised products is that they always result in a market where low price is everything. This kind of market discourages offering more value to the client and the public, and limits the amount of money coming into the profession.

The latter approach provides differentiated, identifiable advantages to the client, and encourages competition on added value, because it is worth paying more for better. This increases the amount of money for archaeology and produces far more public benefit, and it makes archaeology much more

rewarding to do. The approach is well tested, but we need to make it standard practice, rather than the exception.

Professional bodies or institutes can help here. Their role is to promote development of the discipline, and to improve our service to the public. They promote innovation, share knowledge of new techniques between members and, as those techniques become established good practice, embed them in professional requirements. To ensure that the innovation / sharing developments / supporting good practice / setting professional requirements / innovation cycle works (because it is essential to the development of the profession), professional bodies apply entry conditions for membership, set rules of ethical practice that are higher than the general law, and have a process for investigating breaches of the ethical code.

In European countries where archaeology is not directly regulated by the state, professional bodies, with their overriding focus on public service, are well placed to promote this shift of approach. If successful, they can bring archaeologists parity of esteem – and remuneration – with other, better recognised professions. But the problem is that in most of those countries only a minority of archaeologists have agreed to join and be regulated by a professional body: the remainder, while normally honest and skilled, have not had their competence assessed, have not agreed to comply with an ethical code and are not subject to sanctions if found unethical (unprofessional). They therefore undermine rather than support the drive for change and improvement.

This is where we need to make governments step in, to create what is known in the professions as *regulated self-regulation*. In such an instance, members of the professional body agree to the rules with which they will comply, while at the same time governments require participation in said professional body (e.g., by making it a requirement for gaining an archaeological licence). Many governments will be reluctant to take that step, out of fear that it will somehow interfere with a free market. Those fears can be overcome if we can show that the unregulated environment has produced *market failure*. Market failure typically has three characteristics

- *asymmetry of information*: the buyer of a service or product is less able than the provider to tell good from bad
- *credence goods*: the buyer is asked to believe that the product will provide beneficial outcomes somewhere down the line
- *lack of positive externalities*: the actors in the market (the supplier and purchaser) are managing it in a way that those outside the market (typically the public) are not benefiting in the way or to the extent intended

It is not hard to see these characteristics in commercial archaeology in much of Europe. Governments are normally understood not just to have the right to intervene in market failure of this nature, but also to have a duty to do so.

Sharing strategies will make this job much easier. There could be a role for EAA here. For over 20 years it had a Community for Professional Associations in Archaeology. However, that recently closed because its members did not fill (and were unaware of?) vacancies on its committee. Yet the appetite is still there, as illustrated by the 2024 AM's session entitled "Professional Archaeology in Europe: the

state of the issue” organised by *l'Associazione Nazionale Archeologi* with support from the Institute of Archaeologists of Ireland).

The Board and EAA professional members should consider reviving a community for professional bodies. Without an increased emphasis on professionalism, we will not give society the archaeology it deserves, nor will we be valued in the way that we deserve.

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Review

30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome ‘*Persisting with Change*’

Fredrik Dahlberg & Nicoline Schjerven¹

PhD Candidates, University of Gothenburg

Rome, also known as the ‘Eternal City’, proved to be an exceptionally suitable destination for the 30th EAA Annual Meeting. The city's charm lies in its vibrant piazzas, iconic landmarks like the Colosseum and Pantheon, and open-air archaeological parks, all of which can be admired while savouring a delightful lunch at one of the many trattorias. The local transport system in Rome, particularly the buses and metro, made traveling around the city fast, affordable and convenient; one could just ‘blip’ one’s bank card and get a ticket. If private travel suited you more, simply sharing a taxi was also a convenient option and finding an available one was never difficult, either.

Our hotel (along with those of most of our colleagues) was within a short walking distance from the location of the conference: the University of Sapienza. Along the way, there were plenty of options for enjoying a typical Italian breakfast of a *cornetto al pistacchio* or a pastry filled with sweet marmalades, and a foamy cappuccino if needed. The expansive open campus of University of Sapienza was surrounded by buildings of diverse architectural styles and varying degrees of modernity. The main building, located at the far end of the campus, housed key activities such as registration, the helpdesk, and exhibits. One room close to the entrance, was dedicated to the Archaeo-Sexism exhibition, featuring brave testimonies on this particularly important topic. See Figure 28. At the registration desk delegates received the customary gift bag, which contained a program, some advertisements and an item that would prove very useful in the coming days, namely a simple paper hand-fan. However, there was no notebook or pen in the gift bag, much to the chagrin for those who enjoy collecting them.

Being in Rome in August, it was no surprise that temperatures soared into the 30s. The lecture rooms had varying levels of air conditioning, and some were warmer than others. However, most delegates accepted the heightened level of perspiration and the close contact with one’s similarly sweaty neighbours in the lecture halls as part of the experience. The sessions were held in designated lecture rooms in buildings around the campus area. Some of these were a bit easier to find than others. But for the most part there were volunteers that could (perhaps after some head scratching) point you in the right direction.

¹ Editors’ Note: Dahlberg and Schjerven organized their first session together with colleague Giacomo Bilotti (#617 ‘*From Lots of Data to Big Data: Strategies for Quality, Reusability and Accessibility of Databases*’) over the course of the 2024 AM in Rome.

Figure 28. Poster for the Archaeo-Sexism Exhibition. Photo by Evan Skole, with permission.

As expected, the presentations were on a wide range of different topics, representing the diverse aspects of archaeology. The size of the conference and the multitude of sessions ensured that there was always something to capture one's attention. Occasionally, sessions with similar topics were sometimes scheduled at the same time. This made it difficult to choose which session to attend at times. But for us, this was a luxury problem indeed. Most people with whom we interacted were of good spirits and expressed that they were able to listen to some very interesting presentations. However, internet connectivity was a hurdle. Some sessions faced difficulties connecting via Zoom, and online presentations were problematic for many sessions. While the ability to present online has obvious benefits, it may be wise to avoid hybrid sessions in the future as they tend to cause delays in the already tight schedule. Instead, online only sessions could be a better alternative and possibly less disruptive to the schedule.

Figure 29. The Poster Room with digital screens displaying exciting new research. Photo by Elena Peri, with permission.

A floor below the reception area in the main building served as the Poster Room, where all the posters were digitally displayed. See Figure 29. There were a large number of posters and an easier way to search and filter for topics of interest would have been greatly appreciated. Other than that, it was a delight to scroll through all the different posters and read about the interesting new research that is being done.

As first-time session organisers, the overall impression we had was that things went smoother than previously anticipated. We were lucky to have a well air-conditioned room, and the smiles of attendees as they came into the room spoke volumes. Our session, #617 *From Lots of Data to Big Data: Strategies for Quality, Reusability and Accessibility of Databases*, was attended by more delegates than expected, given that it was on Saturday afternoon, a time when many delegates are either already on their way home or a bit exhausted after some intense days. The few technical mishaps we experienced were quickly solved through joint efforts by session organizers, our helpful volunteer and tech savvy presenters. A benefit of organizing a session about databases is the technical know-how in the room!

Refreshments in the form of coffee, water, and delicious pastries were served outside during breaks, providing an opportunity to mingle and socialize with old and new acquaintances. Despite the warm weather, there was plenty of shade from trees on the campus, and there were also tents prepared by the very service-minded waitstaff. See Figure 30.

Figure 30. Having a break and opportunity to socialise with colleagues in the shade. Photo: Fredrik Dahlberg.

The volunteers did an amazing job! They answered questions, gave directions and seemed to really try their best to assist with technical issues during sessions. Volunteers have the unfortunate role of having to bear the brunt of pressure when things do not go according to plan, such as with technical issues during sessions. This task they performed admirably and to the best of their ability. So, a big thank you to all the volunteers that made the conference experience the best possible! Without you, the conference would not be possible.

The AM app was easily accessible and contained all the necessary information about schedules, room locations and live streams of presentations. Other features included the ability to write messages to colleagues and comment on sessions and posters. Besides information about sessions and presentations, the most useful function for us was the maps. Having maps easily accessible in the app, showing everything from the locations of social events to individual floor plans of the different buildings, was an invaluable aid. The app also served as an organiser, allowing participants to save sessions to a personal agenda and plan which sessions to attend directly in the app, making it much easier to organise a daily schedule and to keep track of the talks that you wanted to attend – a huge bonus for that feature.

The social events were included in the conference fee, which was a pleasant surprise as compared to previous AMs. The welcome reception took place at Palatine Hill, offering a stunning view over the Forum Romanum and the Colosseum. Although the line to enter was long and quite packed with people, time flew by in the company of good colleagues, old and new. See Figure 31. After enjoying an Aperol spritz and some sandwiches (some had more than others), spirits were high. The serving staff worked tirelessly to hand out food and drinks to literally thousands of attendees. A warm Italian summer night with friends and colleagues was the perfect start to the conference, and the view of the Colosseum by night was quite spectacular. See Figure 32.

Figure 31. Archaeologist in line excited for the Welcome Reception. Photo by Fredrik Dahlberg.

Figure 32. Colosseum by night, view from the Forum Romanum. Photo by Nicoline Schjerven.

Figure 33. *Pistacchio tiramisù*, enjoyed at one of the many restaurants on proximity to the venue. Photo by Nicoline Schjerven.

The annual party was held at Testaccio Estate, a summer venue with a stage for live music and opportunities to buy food and drinks. Testaccio is named after Mount Testaccio, a small hill made from accumulated pots deposited there during Roman times. It is much larger than one might imagine and was well worth a visit. The party itself was attended by a great number of conference delegates, providing an excellent opportunity to socialize and make new friends.

The culinary delights of Rome were another highlight. Many delegates enjoyed dining at local trattorias and osterias, where they could savour authentic Roman cuisine in a relaxed and friendly atmosphere. The combination of delicious food, excellent wine and warm hospitality made every meal a memorable experience. See Figure 33.

Overall, for us, the 30th EAA AM in Rome was a resounding success. The well-organized conference, coupled with the opportunity to explore one of the world's most fascinating cities made for an unforgettable experience. Delegates left not only with new inspiration from the many excellent presentations, but also having made valuable professional connections and wonderful memories of their time in the Eternal City.

Debate

After Rome, where next for the EAA?

John Carman

University of Birmingham

The simple answer to my question of course is Belgrade in 2025. But I mean more than this. In Budapest in 2023 the EAA Annual Meeting opened with a session concerning the future of archaeology in Europe, but what was presented was very much what could have been heard at any EAA Annual Meeting from 1995 (I know because I said some of those things at various times through the '90s and since).

Over the years the number of sessions – and therefore papers – at the EAA Annual Meeting has grown until now each can only attract a few attendees; the list of those taking place at any one time is far too many to cope with easily. The importance of sessions seems to be judged not on the topic or the quality and originality of contributions, but simply on the number of speakers; other sessions on important issues can be (and are) relegated to poor times and difficult to find rooms. In Rome this year so many sessions were not much more than replays of what has been heard so many times before. Anyone attending who had not been before would have very little inkling of the amount of work, debate and publication over the past few decades on issues such as preventive archaeology, assessing archaeological significance, applications of technology to archaeological projects and/or engagements with communities. Additionally, so many sessions seemed to be no more than tight echo-chambers where those of like mind confirmed each other's established positions. Scope – and time allocated for discussion – was limited and the focus was on presented papers rather than on encouraging exchanges and debate and dissension among participants. The agenda-setting role of keynotes—of using the opportunity to open up discussion of important wide-ranging issues—seems forgotten in favour of reports by senior scholars on their specific projects. No-one would think that the EAA was founded for purposes related to the development of Europe and to promote our discipline as a set of practices and ideas that matter in the world. The EAA has over time lost its way, misplaced its heart and sold its soul: they need to be retrieved.

So, to answer my question, where next?

The first thing is to address issues relating to the Annual Meeting. The number of sessions needs to be reduced, their importance to the discipline improved (markedly) and, therefore, the same needs to be done for the papers presented. There needs to be an upper limit on the number of sessions – ideally no more than five or six concurrently – and each limited to time, perhaps to a maximum of four hours with three as a preference, in order to ensure plenty of time for actual discussion. Session proposals must include a clear statement of the relevance and importance of the session topic to its European (indeed global) audience; without that, it cannot be accepted. Topics of sessions should not be duplicated or overlap with others. Papers for oral delivery should be carefully selected, drawing upon

the wider expertise (especially in the EAA's Advisory Committees) of EAA members, to look for originality, quality and relevance, and to provide a basis for debate and discussion. Sessions should, therefore, become *fora* for debate and discussion of important themes, with all that implies in encouraging differences in approach. This places a burden – but a necessary one – on session organizers and session attendees. Papers not accepted for oral presentation should be presented as posters, and the status of posters – as well as their location and availability – should be enhanced, so as not to disadvantage those offering them, especially in terms of obtaining funding support. Plenaries and the Annual Business Meeting (the latter now no more than an overlong bureaucratic exercise of presenting reports) should be used to debate key issues – to make the policy of the Association on issues such as conflicts affecting archaeology and our colleagues, threats to academic freedom and archaeological education, relations between different kinds of archaeologist, or whatever is identified as important. For too long the Annual Meeting has been merely a place to *talk at* each other rather than what it needs to be – a place where we *confer with* one another over things that matter.

There is a lack of connection between the Annual Meeting and the publications of the Association. The journal (*European Journal of Archaeology*) and this newsletter (*The European Archaeologist*) need to be leaders in presenting the important debates emerging from the Annual Meeting rather than mere reports on aspects of work. The book series should also focus on the topics that matter to archaeologists across the Continent and beyond. All sessions should be thought of as drafts for significant publication outputs and should be treated as such. The EAA imprint on a publication should be a badge of both quality and global importance to archaeologists worldwide: a clear indication that its pages contain material *every* archaeologist should read.

The structure of the Association – especially its Advisory Committees and Communities of specific interest – are a valuable resource and should be used to their fullest effects. The Communities in particular need to take their role in the EAA as a democratic organisation to heart, and offer policy directions for the Association on those issues of significance to them. The Advisory Committees are repositories of expertise, their members chosen by the EAA Executive Board for that purpose: they should be used to advise on responses to issues before the Executive; their role should be emphasized by an enhanced status accorded them at the Annual Meeting.

The EAA is too often presented as non-political. It is indeed non-*party* political nor partisan in other ways. But we cannot deny its political role in promoting archaeology and archaeologists to the wider world, working to protect archaeology and archaeologists from harm, and taking stances in relation to world events that affect archaeological material and the welfare of colleagues. The EAA needs to assert its power and authority: this resides in its membership, and as a democratic body needs to call on that membership for leadership and action. Our motto should be: 'ask not what the Association can do for you, but what you can do for Archaeology'.

But first we need to prepare for a new style of Annual Meeting. In Belgrade next year, we have the opportunity to redesign the Annual Meeting to truly enhance the status of the Association and what it stands for – which is all the archaeologists of Europe and the material on which they work. We need to focus on what matters and rule out mere restatements of what is already known. We need to apply imagination to the structure of sessions and the placing of papers – no more echo-chambers. We need keynotes that set agendas, not merely promote projects. We need also to be bold as to the topics with which we engage and to recognize the influence we can and should wield. The Annual Meeting is our flagship event: let us make it so.

Debate

A response to Carman: After Rome, where next for the EAA?

Eszter Bánffy

EAA President

All critical comments must be appreciated and carefully considered for the sake of their usefulness and possible insights. In John Carman's Debate piece featured in this issue, I find one such useful and insightful observation in that he sees the EAA at a turning point. I too see this, although we may not see eye to eye in the direction to which this points.

John Carman expressed his view that the "EAA has over time lost its way, misplaced its heart and sold its soul", and suggests profound changes to let them be retrieved.

He focuses firstly on the too large number of sessions, suggesting that they should be reduced to no more than five or six parallel sessions. This demand – the consequence of which might not be well considered – would exclude some 90 % of our members from attending our Annual Meeting (AM). This would make the EAA an exclusive, elitist club rather than an association of similarly-focused professionals. Carman is correct that our AMs continue to grow. This is not only the case for popular venues like Rome but also those that had been thought to be "smaller" host destinations, like Belfast in 2023. At this point of EAA's 30-years-long history, the Executive Board had to come to a decision: either we go in the direction of restricting access for further members to attend, or we open the door more widely (meanwhile, boosting the infrastructure and the Prague staff), to match and offer better service to our growing membership. We chose the second option. We choose to remain inclusive. We choose to invite everyone who wishes to share the joys and benefits of this fantastic community.

Further, John Carman complains about the quality of the sessions. He claims that each can attract only a few attendees. I suspect that he did not participate in the meeting in person; had he done so he would have seen that many of the sessions – perhaps the majority – were indeed quite crowded, even in the largest rooms of the venue. The composition – and the merging of similar sessions – is a long-standing and difficult task which falls on the shoulders of many people, principally members of the scientific committee, which consists of local experts and delegates from the Board. I accept his view regarding the Keynote themes on the necessity that these be highly relevant to overarching European and global questions. Currently, the selection of potential Keynotes is concentrated on garnering the top experts in our discipline, whilst considering an optimal balance of geography, gender balance, and the many fields of archaeology. Apart from these factors, the chosen speakers are given the professional courtesy to decide on their topic. To keep or extend the points of selection may be discussed in the near future: we are grateful for the idea and shall put it on the agenda in due course.

I regret the negative impressions about the Annual Members' Business Meeting. However, there are a few circumstances that shape the meeting's structure. First, the detailed Annual Report is always sent to the membership 15 days in advance. Assuming that members will have read it before the

Business Meeting, no details are necessary to repeat. Second, the voting happens later, online, *per rollam*: an achievement introduced since Covid times. There are also still other crucial points worth listening to such as, for example, the announcement of the elections and that of future venues. The meeting is usually reduced in its length and has a shorter agenda. Nevertheless, members' questions, comments or suggestions for themes to discuss are always welcome, if they are sent to the Board in advance. This time, no such suggestions reached us prior to the meeting.

Last but not least, some thoughts about the suggested changes to be applied for Belgrade, to be redesigned. This is a part in Carman's Debate letter which surprised me, as it comes from a long-standing member who has been serving the EAA in different roles. It should be common knowledge that the organisation and preparation of an AM takes no less time than about three years. I am already making efforts to find venues for years ahead of us, to leave ample time for the necessary planning between the Executive Board and the local organisers. Likewise, the discussion and then the decision about the Belgrade meeting was made by my predecessor Felipe Criado-Boado and his Board, back in 2020. The 14 members of the Scientific Committee identified the main themes long ago, and the sessions for these themes are already open for submission. These are circumstances making any suggestion about profound changes for next year, even if they had been thought to be useful, barely feasible.

All in all, I agree in the turning point of the EAA in and after the Rome meeting, in the sense that we now have more than 5000 members and must strive to keep our original inclusive nature despite this growth. In this change of scale, the EAA is determined to remain and act as a socially coherent family, with intellectual and emotional ties among members. The AM is a flagship indeed, but by far not the only important activity that the EAA takes on. For a detailed discussion of these highlights, see the Editors' note in this issue.

In sum, with due respect, I do not share John Carman's view that the EAA has "misplaced its heart and sold its soul." We continue to follow the road decided upon and we possess the understanding and the solidarity to care for our fellow-members, who apparently seem to support for EAA's wider vision, for the well-being of a significant, large, welcoming, and adoptive, recipient.

Community News

Special Visit to Ostia Antica at EAA Rome 2024

Sofia Fonseca

Co-Chair of the EAA Community on Archaeology and Tourism.

On Sunday, September 1st, 2024, EAA attendees participated in a special visit to Ostia Antica, the ancient harbor city of Rome. This event was organized by the EAA Community on Archaeology and Tourism in collaboration with the Ostia Antica Archaeological Park and was made possible thanks to the support of the EAA through the Communities Special Support Fund, to which the Community successfully applied. See Figure 34.

Figure 34. Participants in the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) visit to Ostia Antica. The event featured site and museum visits, expert presentations on heritage management and tourism, and discussions on sustainable practices for cultural heritage sites. Image © Sofia Fonseca.

The visit was a great success, with 50 participants engaging in presentations and site tours focused on the intersection of heritage management and tourism. Sally Foster, Secretary of the EAA, opened the seminar, followed by Sofia Fonseca, Co-Chair of the Community on Archaeology and Tourism. Although Alessandro D'Alessio, Director of the Ostia Antica Archaeological Park, could not be present,

a note from him was read to the audience. Presentations were given by Dario Daffara, Marina Lo Blundo and Alberto Tulli from the Archaeological Park, as well as Alessandro La Porta from CoopCulture. These experts shared insights on preservation, educational programs, and sustainable tourism practices. Participants also had the opportunity to visit the renewed Museum of Ostia and engage in discussions on future site management with specialists Peter Kienzle and Cynthia Dunning Thierstein, both members of the EAA Community on Archaeology and Tourism. See Figures 35-37.

30th annual meeting of the European Association of Archaeologist
Special visit to Ostia antica
1st September 2024

Programme

10:00 Arrival in Ostia

- Introduction by **Sally Foster**, Secretary of EAA
- Intervention by **Sofia Fonseca**, EAA Community Integrating the Management of Archaeological Heritage and Tourism
- Greetings from **Alessandro D'Alessio**, Director of Ostia antica Archaeological Park

11:00 Coffee break

- Cultural heritage preservation in Ostia antica, by **Dario Daffara**, officier of the Park
- Tell and disseminate the archaeological Park, by **Marina Lo Blundo**, officier of the Park
- Exploitation of cultural heritage, by **Alberto Tulli**, officier of the Park
- Educational activities, by **Dario Daffara** and **Alessandro La Porta**, Coopculture
- The voice of Ostia, by **Aldo Marinelli**, "La mia Ostia" magazine

13:00 Lunch

- Visit of the renewed Museum of Ostia
- The management of Ostia, discussion with **Peter Kienzle** and **Cynthia Dunning Thierstein**

16:00 Coffee break

- Visit of the Archaeological Area of Ostia antica

18.00 Return to Rome

OSTIA ANTICA
COOP CULTURE
TEIDUMA
ARCHAEOCONCEPT
EAA 2023
Persisting with change

Figure 35. The program of the special visit to Ostia antica, organized by the EAA Community on Archaeology and Tourism, in collaboration with the Ostia antica Archaeological Park. The visit included expert presentations, site tours, and discussions on heritage management and sustainable tourism practices. Image © Ostia antica Archaeological Park.

Figure 36. Attendees had the opportunity to be guided on a special visit to the renewed Museum of Ostia antica. Image © Sofia Fonseca.

Figure 37. The group during the site tour of the Ostia antica Archaeological Park. Image © Sofia Fonseca.

Given the success of this visit, the EAA Community on Archaeology and Tourism plans to organize annual special visits to archaeological sites during the EAA Conference. These visits will bring together various tourism stakeholders to foster open discussions on tourism and how we can collaborate to achieve a more sustainable and inclusive approach.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our gratitude to the EAA Communities Special Support Fund, as well as to Teiduma and Archeo-concept, for their generous financial support, which made this special visit possible. Additionally, we extend our thanks to the Ostia Antica Archaeological Park and CoopCulture for their invaluable organizational support in facilitating this enriching experience.

In Memoriam

Prof. Timothy Darvill (22 December 1957 – 5 October 2024)

Professor Tim Darvill in the Stonehenge landscape, June 2024.

British archaeologist Professor Timothy Darvill, who will be known to many of you, died after a short illness at the beginning of October 2024. Tim had an illustrious career as a leading prehistorian both at his British university and through the many other posts he held both in the UK and Europe such as Vice-President of the Society of Antiquaries. He was awarded the Order of the British Empire in 2010 for his services to archaeology.

He was a member of the European Association of Archaeologists from its inception, and he very much recognised the value of looking outside of regional boundaries at wider archaeological landscapes and geographies.

My earliest memory of meeting Tim at an EAA Annual Meeting was in Saint Petersburg in 2003. There were a few of us who were visiting the Hermitage Museum on the morning before the conference was due to start. Having travelled from the UK, I and colleagues were very keen to look at the prehistoric archaeological collections. When we eventually found the appropriate rooms along a very long corridor, we were quite taken aback to see that the rooms were closed. We were just about to leave when Tim and some other friends arrived. He immediately said wait here a minute and went off to

find out what was going on. As he had done some fieldwork in Russia, he was able to find out for us that it was just because the person watching the room had gone for a break. Once we got into the room, we then had a fantastic time with Tim describing to everyone what we could see in the archaeological collections on display. This is just one illustration of Tim's ability to pass on knowledge and enthusiasm to not only students but also his peers and colleagues about archaeology in general but also about specific places and time periods.

Tim attended the Annual Meeting in Santiago de Compostela in 1994 where he led a session on Archaeology and Tourism. He was then an active member of the Association throughout and in 1999 he was instrumental in the organization of the Annual Meeting at Bournemouth University (BU) in the UK. He led a session on landscape, the papers for which were written up in a publication entitled 'One land many landscapes: Papers from a session held at the European Association of Archaeologists Fifth Annual Meeting in Bournemouth 1999' published in 2001. The scope of the volume covered many European countries including Russia and the UK. He went on to participate in and lead a range of sessions at the Annual Meetings, such as with Roger Thomas in Barcelona in 2018 on 'What have you found? 'Blank Areas' and the value of negative evidence' which led to a publication in *Antiquity* in 2022. During the pandemic he co-ran sessions on 'Constructive conservation – making monuments useful' and then in Budapest he organised a session on 'The houses of death as ancestral monuments. The archaeology of neolithic long Barrows in Europe' with Jan Turek and others.

He also served the EAA on the Nomination Committee from 2013 to 2016 and since 2022 was on the Public Benefits Advisory Committee.

Tim started his archaeological career with doctoral research on the Neolithic of Wales and southwest England at Southampton University. He then had various roles in the private sector before securing in his early thirties the Chair of Archaeology and Property Development in the Department of Conservation Sciences at what was then Bournemouth Polytechnic. As it later developed as Bournemouth University he became the Director of the Centre for Archaeology, Anthropology and Heritage. The outpouring of messages from former students speaking of Tim as their inspiration as teacher and mentor is indicative of the esteem in which he was held.

He was particularly interested in the Neolithic of Britain and Europe and had a personal interest in the Long Barrows of the Cotswolds area of Britain, as he grew up there. Early in my time at English Heritage I can remember taking Tim's advice about the reconstruction of Uley Long Barrow in Gloucestershire and also on repairs to the dry-stone walling at Stoney Littleton Long Barrow. I can remember us marvelling at some of the original Neolithic dry-stone walling holding up the cairn at Stoney Littleton with me being slightly concerned that our repairs would not look as good as the original! Needless to say, I found Tim's 'Long Barrows of the Cotswolds' book invaluable. He also went on to record short videos on the Gloucester Long Barrows in the care of English Heritage. In one of his many roles outside of his university he was the long-term Chair of the Cotswold Archaeology Trust, having been instrumental in its inception.

He also published many other books and papers, some of which were syntheses of prehistory and some the results of excavation work. He led work for BU at Billown on the Isle of Man, and also excavated in Wales, Malta, and was laterally working on a newly discovered multi-phase long barrow known as The Sisters in Gloucestershire near where he grew up.

Tim's other great interest was of course Stonehenge. He wrote his first book in 2006 entitled 'Stonehenge: The Biography of a Landscape'. Then, in 2008, he and Geoff Wainwright were given permission to carry out a small excavation inside the stone circle, where they looked at the stratigraphy between the outer sarsen circle and the trilithon horseshoe in the area of the original

circles of bluestones, many of which are now missing. In an interim report they speculated about the importance of the bluestones for their healing properties and their early arrival at Stonehenge. Also, from careful reconstruction of Atkinson's earlier stratigraphy, the evidence of Roman material and later cuts into features in the medieval period, they illustrated that Stonehenge has a history as well as a prehistory.

In 2012 Tim collaborated with Mike Parker Pearson, Geoff Wainwright and Peter Marshall on a seminal paper in *Antiquity* entitled 'Stonehenge Remodelled', which provided a suggested chronology based on what was known at the time. Tim's most recent Stonehenge paper 'Keeping Time at Stonehenge' was published in *Antiquity* in 2022. In that paper he argued that new research on the phasing meant that the sarsens could form the basis for a calendar of 365.25 days. I was onsite with Tim when he did the measuring for this piece of work and remember a fairly lively discussion, as I was not convinced that Neolithic people needed a calendar. However, as always, the paper makes interesting reading! Alongside his academic interest in Stonehenge, Tim was part of an innovative project with the Restoration Trust called 'Human Henge: Historic Landscapes and Mental health at Stonehenge and Avebury' where he led walks and other activities in the landscape with small groups with mental health issues, with remarkable results.

Tim was also the co-organiser of the Neolithic Studies Group (NSG) since it began in 1983. This is an amorphous band of enthusiasts mainly from the UK, but with some visitors from Europe and further afield from time to time. The NSG meets for an annual day seminar at the British Museum in November and a fieldtrip every May. We always had a local organiser, but Tim was very instrumental in leading the discussion wherever we were and always with his ranging pole in hand to get that last decent photograph. I was fortunate to be on many of the fieldtrips since 2002 and hosted one in Guernsey in 2006, learning so much about prehistoric sites and landscapes along the way.

I know many of you will have your own personal memories, but Tim will be remembered as an exceptional scholar on Stonehenge, and in the field of archaeology in general, and as a valued friend to the EAA and many other organisations, such as English Heritage and Cotswold Archaeology.

Rest in peace, Tim. We shall all miss your knowledge, enthusiasm and friendship.

Heather Sebire

English Heritage

heather.sebire@english-heritage.org.uk

Announcements

European Journal of Archaeology moving to Research Open format

We are delighted to announce that, from January 2025, the [European Journal of Archaeology](#) will move to a [Research Open](#) publication model.

This means that all *research articles* accepted for publication in the journal from 16 October 2024 will be open access (OA). They will be published with a [Creative Commons](#) licence and freely available to read online.

For the *European Journal of Archaeology* community, open access means that the innovative research published in the journal is **freely** and **permanently** available to all, supporting opportunities for research discoveries. For our authors, open access provides **more exposure, wider reach and greater downloads**, with **75%** of articles published in Cambridge University Press journals receiving **30-50% more citations** than their non-OA equivalents.

We have an OA option for every author: The costs of open access publication will be covered through [agreements between the publisher and the author's institution](#), payment of APCs from grant or other funds, or else waived entirely, ensuring every author can publish and enjoy the benefits of OA. See the journal's [Open Access Options](#) page for available licence options, as well as Cambridge's [FAQs](#) for more information.

Advertising in TEA coming in 2025

As of the Winter 2025 Issue of *TEA*, it will now be possible to purchase paid advertising space.

At present, we suggest the following formats:

Format: A4 interspersed within the text of the newsletter (pdf) and banner-style image on home page of given *TEA* issue (suggested dimensions: 1000 - 1400 px width x 300 px height)

- Price: 300 €
- Limit: up to 3 adverts per issue (adverts over the limit will be held over for the next issue)
- Exemptions:
 - Individual new book advertisements – free of charge; *TEA* will implement a new section called “New books” where authors are welcome to publish summary of their book up to a 350 word limit
 - New book advertisements by a publisher – free of charge under the condition that they offer a discount to EAA Members; if no discount is offered, the normal price applies
 - Regular announcements (not advertising) which are judged to be beneficial to EAA Membership

Please contact EAA Secretariat with any advertising or announcement queries for TEA, as these will be judged on a case-by-case basis.

Theoretical Archaeology Group 45th Annual Meeting

Bournemouth, 13-15 December 2024

Sessions + Call for Papers

Below are all the sessions accepted for TAG45. Click on their titles for full details, including emails of the organisers.

The Call for Papers is open until October 1st 2024. Please submit your papers directly to the session organisers. If you cannot find a session that suits your paper contact the TAG organisers here to be considered for the general session.

Sessions

[S1. Materiality, metaphor, phenomenology: reconstructing Chris Tilley's thought and contemporary archaeological theory](#)

[S2. "Does Anybody Ever Listen!?" – Outrage as Method, Evolving Activist Archaeology](#)

[S3. Towards an Archaeology of Cosiness: exploring the lines between comfort, utility, and beyond](#)

[S4. Discomfort in Archaeological Practices: Ethical, social and personal challenges](#)

[S5. Tales as Old as Time: Archaeological Storytelling for Research Dissemination](#)

[S6. Archaeology of Awe: Being moved by being in the world](#)

[S7. Re-Peopling Submerged Prehistory: The Human Dimension in Palaeolandscape Evolution](#)

[S8. \(Re\) conceptualising the Past? Evolution of the imagined/invented/\(re\)created Past](#)

[S9. Archaeology & the Media in the Twenty-First Century](#)

[S10. Evolution In Rock Art Theory: Recent Advances in Understanding Images](#)

[S11. Sites, monuments and their landscapes: new perspectives and new narratives](#)

[S12. Skyscapes in Prehistory: evolution, convolution or involution?](#)

[S13. \(R\)Evolution: theoretical approaches to death and dying in the prehistoric and protohistoric Mediterranean \(7000-700 BCE\)](#)

[S14. Evolution.](#)

[S15. Thinking Through Plants/Thinking With Plants: Archaeologies of Vegetal Becoming](#)

[S16. \(I\)Legible Landscapes?](#)

[S17. Excavating the Collection: New ‘evolutions’ in the Archaeology of Museum Collections](#)

[S18. We’ve talked the talk, can we walk the walk? Approaches and actions to encouraging diverse language representation in archaeology/academia](#)

[S19. Moving away from forwards: Reassessing the metaphorical structuring of evolutionism in Archaeological thought](#)

[S20. Mortuary Memes: Advances in the Digital Public Archaeology of Death](#)

[S21. Ancestor? We hardly know her! Rethinking ancestors in archaeology](#)

[S22. Evolving Practice? Knowledge Production and Intercultural Collaboration in Archaeology](#)

[S23. Narrating the Past: Exploring Archaeological Storying and Creativity](#)

[S24. Living \(and Working\) in Times of Unprecedented Change: A Speculative Design Workshop for Archaeology in the 21st Century](#)

[S25. Heritage Therapy in Theory and Practice: Using Archaeology for Recovery](#)

[S26. Exploring Human-Animal Entanglements in Archaeology: A More-Than-Human Approach](#)

[S27. Experimental archaeology: a useful methodology for researching the evolution of cognitive and behavioural complexity?](#)

[G. General Session](#)

[P. Poster Session](#)

2024 Pitt Rivers Lecture

Housing the future dead: the new British wave of long barrow construction

Dr Kenny Brophy

University of Glasgow

Date: Tuesday 29 October 2024

Time: 7:00pm (Displays and networking from 6:30pm)

Location: This free public lecture will be delivered live in the Fusion Building, Talbot Campus, Bournemouth University, BH12 5BB, and will also be available via Zoom.

Abstract

Exactly 120 years after Pitt Rivers was undertaking his seminal excavation and dismantlement of Wor Barrow, a new long barrow was built in Wessex. Located at All Cannings, not far from West Kennet, The Long Barrow (as this site is known) is a columbarium, that is, a megalithic structure built to store cremated human remains in a variety of receptacles, stored on stone shelves called niches. This Neolithic initiative inspired a relative boom in new barrows being constructed across the UK, with six barrow columbaria now open in England, and others being constructed, including the first one in Scotland. These contain grave goods, a few have solstice alignments, and most have their own standing stones or earthworks. In this lecture I will explore this new phase of barrow construction based on visits, interviews, and documentary research. To what extent are these monuments and associated practices inspired by Neolithic monuments, and why is the barrow such a resilient concept?

About the presenter

Kenny Brophy is a Senior Lecturer in archaeology at the University of Glasgow. He has almost three decades of experience of researching various aspects of the British Neolithic with a particular focus on mainland Scotland and cursus monuments. Researching and blogging as the Urban Prehistorian, for the last decade he has focused increasingly on the contemporary relevance and resilience of prehistory, including the ways that prehistoric architecture, practices, and material culture continue to be replicated today.

For further details, registration, and updates please visit the [Pitt Rivers Lecture Eventbrite page](#).

Call for General Editor, European Journal of Archaeology

The *European Journal of Archaeology*, the official journal of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) and published by Cambridge University Press, is seeking to appoint a new General Editor, to take up office in September 2025, following the retirement of the current General Editor.

The *European Journal of Archaeology* is a broad, well recognised and well cited archaeology journal, currently published four times a year. Starting in 2025, the journal will be published fully Open Access. The editorial work is carried out by the General Editor, assisted by a Deputy Editor, Reviews Editors and an Editorial Board.

The General Editor chairs the Editorial Board and liaises on regular basis with the EAA Executive Board. The Editorial Board normally meets once a year at the Annual Meeting but most of its work is done by email. All production and distribution work is undertaken by Cambridge University Press.

The General Editor will be responsible for

- taking a proportion of papers through the *EJA* editorial peer review process to a final recommendation
- editing final papers to improve the clarity of arguments and quality of English
- checking and correcting proofs as required and returning them to the agreed Publisher's schedule
- soliciting high quality manuscripts for the *Journal*
- acting as an ambassador for the *EJA* at conferences and other events
- Supporting the work of the Reviews Editors

The General Editor is required to be able to work to deadlines, have excellent communication skills, have an ability to carry out editorial tasks based upon prior editorial experience and a breadth of interests, and to work remotely as part of a larger editorial team. Candidates will have specialist expertise in one or more areas of European archaeology and heritage but will also be expected to work outside their own specialist fields of expertise.

The *EJA* is published mainly in English (though articles in French and German are also accepted), and the General Editor must be fluent – though not necessarily a native speaker – in English. Applicants who are not native speakers should indicate how they will deal with the issue of language checking and improvement, where necessary.

The term of office is three years, renewable if desired, and would commence in September 2025, following a six-months handover period. To enable recruitment of an appropriate successor, the notice period is 12 months.

The General Editor will receive an honorarium of €2000 per annum.

The General Editor will be expected to be a member of the EAA, and will be required to attend the Editorial Board meeting which takes place at the start of each EAA Annual Meeting (late August – early September). Both the EAA membership fee and the Annual Meeting registration fee are to be paid by the General Editor themselves, while full travel costs and (part of, depending on current EAA reimbursement policy) accommodation will be covered by the EAA.

We are interested in hearing from those with experience in all areas of European archaeological research who have a vision for the development of the *Journal*, as well as the organisational skills to manage the day to day editorial work.

You are welcome to contact the current *EJA* Editor, Cate Frieman (ejeditor@e-a-a.org), for an informal talk about the position.

If you would like to apply, please email Bisserka Gaydarska, ExB member monitoring Publications (publications@e-a-a.org) and submit your CV as well as a statement no longer than 1000 words outlining your relevant experience and why you would like to be General Editor for the *European Journal of Archaeology*.

The deadline for the receipt of applications is 1 December 2024. Shortlisted candidates will be interviewed online in January – February 2025.

10th World Archaeological Congress 2025

Darwin, Australia

We warmly invite you to join us at the 10th World Archaeological Congress (WAC-10) hosted by Flinders University, 22–28 June 2025.

WAC-10 is an opportunity to collaborate with colleagues and friends from around the world and contribute to global policy making. People from more than 70 countries participate in WAC Congresses.

- Diverse academic program that includes all forms of archaeology.
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- Cultural workshops, social events and policy-making.
- Support for Indigenous people, students and those from low-income countries.
- Selected papers published in Springer's One World Archaeology series.

Claire Smith
Academic Secretary
Contact: claire.smith@flinders.edu.au

Major (Moogy) Sumner AM
Chair, Indigenous Elders Committee

For more
information
about WAC-10

www.worldarchaeologicalcongress.com/wac10/

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